

MASTER STPE

International Master in Geosciences

Year 2025-2026

M2 internship thesis

Field of study: Climatology

**A TYPOLOGY OF LOCAL HOURLY WET SPELLS ACROSS
SOUTHEASTERN FRANCE, RÉUNION AND FRENCH GUIANA:
DRIVERS AND VARIABILITY**

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Remerciements

Je n'ai jamais été particulièrement doué pour exprimer ma gratitude envers les personnes qui me soutiennent dans le cadre de mes études ou de ma vie personnelle, mais je tiens néanmoins à le faire ici puisque ce sont eux qui, plus ou moins indirectement, ont participé à l'élaboration de ce mémoire. Etant donné que je m'attèle pour la première fois à cet exercice (que je ne trouve pas forcément si élémentaire), je leur demande de me concéder un minimum d'indulgence...

Merci Vincent d'avoir fait naître (et d'avoir entretenu) en moi un engouement certain et indéfectible pour les sciences du climat. Depuis la première heure du cours *Bases de la climatologie* durant la deuxième année de licence jusqu'à l'écriture de ces lignes, vous avez considérablement nourri la qualité de mon travail d'étudiant. Que ce soit par la ferveur de votre enseignement ou à travers votre implication dans mon encadrement, je ne compte plus vos conseils ingénieux ni les heures que vous m'avez consacré. J'apprécie votre exigence, votre manière de formuler les concepts et de les articuler entre eux, de même que votre légendaire esprit d'escalier (si, si!). Merci également de m'avoir laissé des dizaines et des dizaines de pages remplies d'idées jetées pêle-mêle et intersectées par de multiples lignes de code, comme des jalons indélébiles de l'intensité et de la fréquence de nos entrevues. Enfin, je vous suis reconnaissant de m'avoir ouvert la voie (plus ou moins tortueuse, certes) vers le monde de la recherche scientifique, auquel j'ai hâte de contribuer, même dans les plus modestes proportions.

Merci Philippe de m'avoir encadré durant ces deux mois au CNRM et d'avoir constamment veillé à ce que tout se déroule au mieux au cours de ce séjour à Toulouse. Bien évidemment, le stage est passé vite mais j'ai tout de même la sensation d'avoir appris et réalisé pleins de choses. Tu es probablement la personne dotée du meilleur esprit de synthèse que j'ai pu rencontrer et cela m'a beaucoup aidé, non seulement pour mûrir les résultats mais aussi pour les présenter à l'équipe. Bien que je sois navré de t'avoir contraint à envoyer plus de cinquante mails pour planifier mon arrivée, le jeu en valait assurément la chandelle.

Merci Erwan pour la gentillesse et la patience dont tu as fait preuve à mon égard. De la même manière, tous tes précieux conseils m'ont été extrêmement utiles, que ce soit concernant ce travail de mémoire ou bien ma candidature au contrat doctoral. Je te remercie également pour tes encouragements et ta bonne humeur tout au long de ma venue, au plaisir de se revoir bientôt.

Plus généralement, un grand merci à l'équipe TROPICS qui m'a accueilli dans ses couloirs parfois étouffants de chaleur mais toujours remplis de sourires. Un grand merci à Fleur pour son dévouement, Dominique pour son zèle ("*Sky is the limit*"), Catherine, Clarisse, Léopold, Emma, Najda, Florence, Florent... Vous vous êtes intéressés à mon travail, m'avez mis en confiance et formez la meilleure équipe du labo en (presque) toute objectivité. Mention spéciale à Nathan avec qui j'ai pu m'évader grimper certains weekends dans les Pyrénées. Je ne pensais pas gravir la dent d'Orlu en solo intégral sur un coup de tête décidé la veille au soir... Bon courage pour boucler la fin de ton manuscrit; je te souhaite ensuite d'enrouler le plus gros thermique de ta vie en Bolivie d'ici quelques mois.

Merci aux trois cenglistes que je n'ai pas beaucoup vus ces derniers temps mais dont les paroles et la compagnie me donneront constamment un élan de motivation. Explicitement, merci Luca de m'avoir emmené grimper sur de superbes (faux) prises sèches (faux) le long des berges de la Garonne et de m'avoir fait découvrir la ville rose, notamment sa fibre "artistique". Merci Jules pour les discussions scientifiques et les premières ascensions que nous avons partagées en montagne et ailleurs. Il me tarde que tu m'inities à ton envolée *pyrénéiste*. Bravo Alice pour ton courage et la préservation de ton enthousiasme durant ces dernières semaines. J'ai hâte de graver de nouveaux souvenirs mémorables avec vous prochainement.

Merci à mes parents pour leur soutien vis-à-vis de mes choix professionnels et l'attention qu'ils me témoignent. Mes pensées vont naturellement à mon père ayant toujours fait preuve d'une grande ouverture d'esprit et bien-sûr à ma mère, qui a toujours sû m'aiguiller justement dans toutes mes entreprises.

Merci ma Lise d'être une fiancée remarquable à tout point de vue. Je ne sais plus comment te remercier pour ton engagement sincère et intarissable dans notre vie à deux. Sans tes conseils, tes relectures avisées et ton soutien sans faille, je n'aurais tout simplement pas accompli ce que j'ai accompli aujourd'hui. Grâce à ton petit grain de folie et tes *propres* expressions géniales, je n'ai jamais été aussi heureux que depuis notre rencontre, bientôt sept ans en arrière. Merci pour tous nos débats, nos discussions profondes, nos sorties en plein air, nos éclats de rires, nos projets communs... Tous ces moments ont largement participé à façonner et consolider tant mes qualités personnelles qu'académiques. Je suis particulièrement fier de toi et te considère comme une source d'inspiration irréfutable.

Abstract

Rainfall is an intrinsically intermittent variable in space and time, combining occurrence and intensity as two distinct properties that can be here treated as quasi-independent at the sub-daily timescale. Building upon the canonical wet spells (CWSs) typology established by [Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025](#) from 3.5 million local hourly wet spells (WSs) across the tropical and subtropical belt, this study transposes and extends their methodology to three climatologically contrasted regions: southeastern France (SEF) and two French overseas territories (OTs), namely Réunion island (REU) and French Guiana (GUI). The analysis relies on hourly rain gauges networks, as well as on ERA5 reanalysis, a tropical cyclones (TCs) catalog from IBTrACS, and intraseasonal anomalies products. We use these datasets to characterize the atmospheric drivers and variability of WSs across diurnal to interannual timescales. The reassignment of local wet spells to the seven pre-existing CWS centroids reveals a fair consistency in their statistical properties (duration, mean and maximum intensity, frequency) across all three study areas, while capturing regional specificities, notably a slight decrease in mean intensity and increase in mean duration of WSs within the extratropical region. In SEF, a dynamic clustering of rain gauges based on the contribution of each CWS to the 30-day running amount identifies three subregions with distinct annual cycles, illustrating also how geographical parameters such as relief and distance to the coast modulate the fingerprint of CWSs. Regarding OTs, TCs in REU predominantly contribute to the longest and most intense CWS (#7), accounting for 10-50% of the local total amount, while CCEWs play a significant and contrasted role in triggering WSs in both REU and GUI, with their overlapping phases enhancing both rainfall and CWSs occurrence probability. Local thermodynamic composites show that all CWSs require positive anomalies in total column water vapor and convective available potential energy alongside reduced convective inhibition at onset; yet the temporal scales and amplitudes of these anomalies vary significantly between study areas and CWSs. The diurnal cycle exerts a strong control on short and intense CWSs (#2 and #4), with afternoon peaks in SEF and REU and a more complex modulation in GUI where long-lasting CWSs exhibit nocturnal peaks aligned with land-sea breeze dynamics. Interannual trend analysis over SEF (1993-2024) demonstrates that the hourly timescale is crucial to detect rainfall intensification under anthropogenic warming, revealing a significant +4% increase in the mean hourly intensity of wet hours alongside a -35% decrease in their frequency and -6% in mean duration of WSs. These changes compensate and thus are not visible at the daily timescale. Most intense CWSs (#2, #4, #7) exhibit super-Clausius-Clapeyron (CC) effect at high percentiles, while shorter CWSs (#1, #3) tend to follow a sub-CC behavior. While this work presents only a selection of results to illustrate the analytical potential of the CWSs framework across very contrasted climatic settings, it demonstrates that this typology reveals a three-dimensional characterization of WSs (duration, spatial extent and intensity), thus offering a comprehensive framework for future climate projections and hydro-meteorological risk assessment.

Keywords: Rainfall types · Sub-daily · Intensity · Duration · Seasonal and diurnal cycles · Tropical cyclones · Convectively-coupled equatorial waves · Extreme rainfall · Clausius-Clapeyron scaling

Résumé étendu

Les précipitations se distinguent de champs continus tels que la température ou la pression par leur intermittence, à la fois dans l'espace et dans le temps. En conséquence, elles combinent deux propriétés fondamentales, à savoir l'occurrence (ou la fréquence, i.e. *quand pleut-il?*) et l'intensité (i.e. *combien pleut-il?*). En illustrant, à partir des cumuls horaires du réseau de pluviomètres de Météo-France, le fait que plus de 99.5% des évènements pluvieux durent moins de 24h (et que plus de 50% d'entre eux durent seulement 1h, cf. Figure 3), nous montrons qu'il est possible de décomposer le cumul des évènements pluvieux comme le produit d'une fréquence et d'une intensité spécifiques à cette échelle temporelle. Conceptuellement, cette approche est intéressante, notamment car elle permet de différencier les évènements pluvieux à partir de certaines de leurs caractéristiques intrinsèques (fréquence, durée, intensité moyenne et maximale, emprise spatiale des secteurs arrosés, entre autres), en se fondant sur l'hypothèse que les échelles spatio-temporelles des mécanismes pilotant la fréquence et l'intensité ne sont pas nécessairement les mêmes. De fait, cette distinction apparaît pertinente dans la mesure où, par définition, il existe différents types de pluies (e.g. stratiformes vs convectives) dont les processus ne dépendent pas, *a priori*, des mêmes échelles spatio-temporelles.

Dans cette étude, nous réutilisons la typologie de [Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025](#), distinguant sept grands régimes de pluie (CWSs, *canonical wet spells* en anglais) à partir de 3.5 millions de d'évènements pluvieux (WSs, *wet spells* en anglais, définis à l'échelle locale du pluviomètre comme des séquences d'heures pluvieuses ≥ 1 mm consécutives) distribués au sein de divers fuseaux tropicaux et sub-tropicaux. Un premier objectif consiste à transposer cette classification à trois territoires très contrastés du point de vue climatologique, à savoir le Sud-Est de la France métropolitaine (SEF) ainsi que deux territoires d'outre-mer (OTs, *overseas territories* en anglais): la Réunion (REU) et la Guyane française (GUI). À partir de l'extraction d'environ 1.25 million de WSs répartis sur plus de 500 pluviomètres sur les trois régions d'étude (1993-2025 en SEF, 1998-2025 dans les deux OTs, cf. Figure 1), nous réattribuons chaque WSs à un des sept CWSs par le biais d'une distance euclidienne. La projection dans l'espace durée-intensité des CWSs du SEF (cf. Figure 2) respecte la trame générique définies au sein des tropiques tout en enregistrant un signal attendu en dehors de la zone tropicale de légère baisse de l'intensité et de légère hausse de la durée, en moyenne pour tous les CWSs. De même, les effectifs de fréquence relative sont assez bien respectés entre les régions d'études (cf. Table 1.1) alors que rien ne présuppose cela dans la définition initiale des centroïdes.

Cette classification des situations pluvieuses offre un cadre compact pour étudier la variabilité des WSs et analyser les échelles spatio-temporelles des systèmes et processus associés à leur occurrence. Pour ce faire, nous nous appuyons sur les réanalyses atmosphériques ERA5 ainsi que sur l'archive IBTrACS référençant les occurrences de cyclones tropicaux (TCs, *tropical cyclones* en anglais) et sur un catalogue d'anomalies intra-saisonnières, contenant également la contribution de différents modes intrasaisonniers, dont certaines ondes équatoriales (CCEWs, *convectively-coupled equatorial waves* en anglais), fourni par les responsables de la plateforme MISVA (Real-time Monitoring and forecast of IntraSeasonal VARIability). Dans le cas spécifique du SEF qui présente à lui seul une grande variabilité climatologique, nous effectuons une classification des pluviomètres en fonction de la contribution saisonnière des CWSs au total de pluie sur des segments glissants de 30 jours localement. Du fait de sa profondeur temporelle (32 ans climatologiques), nous prenons aussi le SEF comme région d'étude pour une analyse de tendance interannuelle sur les caractéristiques des WSs. La loi de Clausius-Clapeyron (CC, prévoyant une hausse de +7% du contenu en vapeur d'eau admissible dans l'air par °K de réchauffement) permet de relier ces analyses au réchauffement climatique anthropique (AGW, *anthropogenic global warming* en anglais) à l'échelle horaire versus à l'échelle quotidienne.

Les résultats de la régionalisation des pluviomètres du SEF montrent une partition cohérente en trois sous-régions (cf. Figure 5), dont le comportement diffère sensiblement selon les CWSs et la saison (cf. Figure 6). On distingue ainsi: (1) TBSA-WCC (bassin toulousain, Alpes du Sud et côte Ouest de la Corse), caractérisée par une contribution dominante des CWSs courts peu intenses (#1 et #3) et peu modulés par le cycle annuel. (2) CLRAM-NC (Cévennes, Languedoc, Roussillon, Alpes-Maritimes et Corse du Nord), marquée par une contribution saisonnière très marquée des CWSs longs et intenses (#6 et #7) au printemps

et surtout en automne, cohérente avec l'orientation privilégiée E-SE des versants concernés. (3) RVMC-IC (vallée du Rhône, littoral méditerranéen et intérieur montagneux de la Corse), dont le comportement se rapproche de la moyenne de l'ensemble du SEF. Les CWSs les plus courts et intenses (#2 et #4) se produisent uniquement en été en en début d'automne sur les trois sous-régions mais sont légèrement plus fréquents au sein de cette dernière, ce qui semble cohérent avec le fait qu'elle soit la plus chaude en moyenne durant l'été boréal. Dans les OTs, la saisonnalité des CWSs est nettement moins contrastée et suit globalement celle du total de pluie (cf. Figure 7), bien que des différences subsistent, notamment entre les CWSs longs et courts en GUI, dont les pics de contribution se positionnent respectivement au début et à la fin de la saison humide.

Les analyses portant sur les mécanismes à grande échelle dans les OTs montrent qu'en REU, les TCs se concentrent très majoritairement au sein du CWS #7 au sein duquel ils représentent entre 30 et 80% du cumul total localement et 5 à 30% des jours pluvieux correspondants. La contribution des TCs au cumul total reste néanmoins deux à trois fois plus faible et assez homogène dans les autres CWSs. En dehors des occurrences cycloniques, les composites en REU révèlent des interactions claires avec la circulation extratropicale (cf. Figure 8), à l'image d'un front convectif estival associé à une perturbation de moyenne latitude (CWS #4) ou d'un talweg tropical amplifié par l'anticyclone des Mascareignes qui transite plus au Sud (CWS #7). En GUI, les structures sont au contraire essentiellement zonales et montrent de façon assez systématique une propagation d'anomalie d'eau précipitable vers l'ouest et un flux convergent dans les basses couches. D'autres composites suggèrent l'activité d'une ou plusieurs CCEWs, dont les anomalies positives d'eau précipitable coïncident parfaitement avec le jour d'occurrence de l'évènement, bien que plus ou moins intenses et plus ou moins étendues selon les CWSs (cf. Figures 11 et 12). La superposition des phases d'ondes actives simultanément sur la pluie quotidienne tend à amplifier de façon systématique la probabilité d'occurrence à la fois des WSs et des CWSs (cf. Figure 13), notamment les plus intenses (#2, #4, #6 et #7), tandis qu'elle ne produit pas d'effet significatif sur le CWS le moins intense (#1).

À l'échelle locale et infra-journalière, les composites montrent que l'occurrence de tout CWS implique une anomalie positive d'eau précipitable et d'instabilité convective ainsi qu'une anomalie négative (ou une baisse) d'inhibition convective à l'heure du déclenchement (cf. Figure 14). Néanmoins, les échelles temporelles et les amplitudes de ces anomalies diffèrent significativement entre les régions et entre les CWSs. En particulier, les CWSs courts et intenses (#2 et #4) se distinguent par une anomalie d'inhibition convective positive avant le déclenchement et par les plus fortes anomalies d'instabilité convective, dont la montée et la dissipation sont nettement plus rapides en SEF (de l'ordre de $\pm 6h$) que dans les OTs. Par ailleurs, le cycle diurne module aussi fortement l'heure d'initiation de ces mêmes CWSs (cf. Figure 15) avec un pic de convection l'après-midi dans les trois régions. A l'inverse, les CWSs longs (#6 et #7) présentent un cycle diurne quasiment plat en SEF mais un pic nocturne bien marqué en GUI, qui se superpose parfaitement avec les dynamiques de brise terre-mer observées en surface (cf. Figure 16).

L'analyse de tendance sur le SEF montre que l'échelle horaire détecte un signal de modification des WSs en lien avec l'AGW. On observe une hausse significative de +4% de l'intensité moyenne des heures pluvieuses conjuguée à une baisse de -35% de leur fréquence et une diminution de -6% de la durée moyenne des WSs. Nous mettons en évidence que ces modifications se compensent et ne sont pas visibles à l'échelle journalière (cf. Figure 18). En regardant par CWS, nous montrons que les plus intenses (#2, #4 et #7) enregistrent l'intensification la plus prononcée, avec un effet "super-CC" sur les percentiles élevés ($\geq P95$), tandis que les CWSs courts et peu intenses (#1 et #3) enregistrent plutôt un effet "sous-CC" (cf. Figure 19).

Cette approche confirme, à travers une sélection de résultats sur des régions climatologiquement très contrastées, le potentiel analytique des CWSs. Nous illustrons notamment comment cette typologie arrive à capturer un tryptique (entre durée, emprise spatiale et intensité) intrinsèque à la variabilité spatio-temporelle des précipitations, permettant de documenter *a posteriori* de multiples propriétés des WSs à partir de caractéristiques non incluses au départ dans la classification. Ce cadre semble ainsi offrir une base robuste pour de futures projections climatiques ainsi que pour l'évaluation des risques hydro-météorologiques.

Mots-clés: Types de pluie · Infra-journalier · Intensité · Durée · Cycles saisonnier et diurne · Cyclones tropicaux · Ondes équatoriales couplées à la convection · Pluies extrêmes · Loi de Clausius-Clapeyron

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Introduction

Contrary to continuous variables such as temperature or pressure, which can be solely defined by a single scalar value, rainfall is an intrinsically intermittent variable, both in space and time (Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025). In consequence, rainfall combine two distinct properties, namely (1) occurrence (i.e. *when does it rain?*) and (2) intensity (i.e. *how much does it rain?*). While these two components actually contribute to the total amount, the physical mechanisms driving them are not necessarily the same. In addition, when the analytical timescale is fine enough to capture the discontinuous nature of wet events, occurrence and intensity share only a marginal common variance, which in turn allows their separate analysis (cf. Section 1.2.1). Thus, it is possible to decompose the cumulative amount recorded over a given period into the respective contribution of these two components (Biasutti and Yuter, 2013). For instance, a daily amount can be decomposed as the product of the frequency of wet hours times the mean rainfall intensity during these hours.

Basically, that kind of decomposition is not merely a statistical exercise. It reflects the fact that the overwhelming majority of rainfall events – referred to hereafter as wet spells (WSs) and defined through local rain gauge scale as consecutive wet hours receiving at least 1 mm of rainfall – almost never last 24 consecutive hours or more¹, which justifies the use of the hourly timescale to properly disentangle these two characteristics (Trenberth, Zhang, and Gehne, 2017; Dunkerley, 2018). At the daily timescale, frequency and mean intensity are indeed more intertwined, since a single wet day may encompass several distinct rainfall episodes of very different natures, thus blurring the physical interpretation of their respective contributions to the total amount. This aspect may be quite critical, typically for impact studies, since the sub-daily distribution of wet hours among a day will likely not produce the same impact on society depending on whether it is concentrated or spread out over time² (Hettiarachchi, Wasko, and Sharma, 2018). For instance, a very brief but intense WS occurring over an almost completely impervious city can lead to a much greater risk than a more diffuse WS, even if both ultimately result in the same cumulative daily amount.

Equally, this distinction appears physically meaningful because the variability of the main WSs characteristics (i.e. duration, frequency, mean and maximum intensity, spatial extent of rain-affected areas) is not necessarily driven by the same atmospheric conditions and does not depend on the same spatio-temporal scales of motion (Orlanski, 1975). For instance, a wintertime frontal rain system differs radically from a convective summer thunderstorm or a tropical cyclone (TC) with regards to the characteristics defined earlier. Stratiform rainfall, typically associated with large-scale dynamics, tends to be weakly to moderately intense but long-lasting, while convective rainfall can be extremely intense but is usually short-lived (Tremblay, 2005), except when embedded within mesoscale convective systems (MCS) or TCs (Houze et al., 2015). This duality motivates the idea that decomposing total rainfall through the lens of individual WSs properties provides a relevant basis to link our conceptual and statistical approach (relying uniquely on accumulated hourly amounts at the beginning) to that more physically grounded framework.

Based on these premises, Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025 applied a systematic analysis of 3.5 million local WSs extracted from a network of 1123 rain gauges distributed across the tropical and subtropical zone (30°N-30°S), covering a wide range of climates from arid to very wet. Using a k -means clustering of the 24-hourly rainfall profiles from the onset of each WS – after square-root transformation and normalization – they identified seven canonical wet spells (CWSs) explaining approximately 75-80% of the variance of total amount and duration, and 60-70% of the variance of mean and maximum intensity across the full dataset. This typology reveals the existence of very short and quite negligible WSs (CWSs #1 and #3) in terms of total amount but which are the most frequent by far, short but very intense WSs associated with small spatial scales and the most frequent hourly extremes (CWSs #2 and #4), a moderately long and moderately intense WS a bit above the average properties of the full set (CWS #5), and two long-lasting, quite intense

¹This is the case for more than 99.5% of all wet spells across the three study areas considered in this work (cf. Section 1.2.1).

²This principle can be extended to other examples, such as a given seasonal amount which does not have the same impact on crops according to the intraseasonal distribution and the mean intensity of wet days (Hernandez et al., 2014), showing that the use of the daily timescale can be totally relevant for other scientific purposes, especially seasonal predictability studies.

WSs that cover large spatial scales and contribute predominantly to daily extremes (CWSs #6 and #7).

The present study builds upon this framework and pursues three main purposes:

- (1) The first aim is to transpose the CWSs methodology to a climatologically distinct region outside the tropical belt, namely southeastern France (SEF). This area was selected because it already constitutes the focus of preliminary work on extreme daily rainfall (Chetrit, 2025), because its orography is highly contrasted – ranging from the Massif Central and the Alps to the Mediterranean coastline and Corsica – and because it exhibits a particularly marked and complex seasonality compared to most tropical areas. SEF is also notable for producing WSs of very different natures, from short and highly localized convective events to long-lasting and spatially extensive episodes associated with orographic forcing, such as the well-documented *épisodes cévenols* (Boudevillain et al., 2011; Molinié et al., 2012). More broadly, the Mediterranean region constitutes a recognized hotspot of climate change, warming approximately 1,4 times faster than the global mean temperature increase (Cusack and Cox, 2025). Moreover, the long-term evolution of precipitation variability in this region remains yet highly uncertain (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2025; Iliopoulou et al., 2026). Besides, the density and temporal depth of the Météo-France hourly rain gauges network in this area offer a particularly favorable observational context for applying the CWSs approach.
- (2) The second objective is to apply the same methodology to two French overseas territories (OTs): Réunion island (REU) and French Guiana (GUI). Although both are influenced by the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), they differ substantially in their climatological contexts. On the one hand, REU is a mountainous tropical island in the southwestern Indian Ocean, exposed to persistent south-easterly trade winds and to TCs activity during the austral summer (Cornillault, 2025). On the other hand, GUI is a humid equatorial territory with very little relief and no exposure to TCs and where rainfall is primarily driven by the seasonal migration of the ITCZ and by convective processes linked to land-sea interactions and frequently driven by the diurnal cycle (Ramirez Nina, Dias, and Silva Dias, 2025). Examining these two territories alongside SEF allows for a meaningful comparison of CWSs properties and their atmospheric drivers across very different climatic and geographical settings.
- (3) The third purpose is to examine the interannual variability of WSs characteristics (including mean and maximum intensity, frequency, and duration) in the context of the ongoing anthropogenic global warming (AGW). In this respect, the Clausius-Clapeyron (CC) law predicts an increase of approximately $+7\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$ in atmospheric water vapor content, which thermodynamically supports an intensification of short-duration rainfall extremes (Fowler, Lenderink, et al., 2021). However, the observed response of rainfall to warming remains difficult to detect unambiguously, as it involves competing effects between thermodynamic and dynamic multi-scale forcings, particularly in the case of extreme events (Allen and Ingram, 2002; Held and Soden, 2006; Lenderink and Meijgaard, 2008); Isolating each CWS independently provides a way to assess whether the intensification signal differs across WSs types, and more specifically whether the most intense and short-lived ones (expected to be the most sensitive to thermodynamic forcing) exhibit a stronger ("*super-CC*") or a weaker ("*sub-CC*") CC relationship than longer and *a priori* more large-scale driven and dynamically controlled WSs.

This study is organized as follows. Chapter 1 presents the datasets and methodological framework, including for the data the rain gauge networks, the reanalysis products and the TCs/equatorial waves³ catalogs. Concerning the methods, we describe CWSs attribution procedure, spatial clustering of SEF stations, intraseasonal anomaly extraction, as well as composite and trend detection methods. Chapter 2 presents the main results, organized around the regional and seasonal fingerprint of CWSs across the three study areas, the large-scale atmospheric drivers of CWSs occurrence in the two OTs, and the sub-daily triggering mechanisms linked to CWSs onset. Chapter 3 discusses the interannual variability of WSs characteristics and their evolution under the influence of AGW and compares it to the expected increase by means of CC-scaling. Finally, a brief conclusion summarizes the key findings and outlines perspectives for future work.

³These waves, coupled with convection (both dynamically and thermodynamically), form coherent structures known as convectively-coupled equatorial waves (CCEWs). They result from a “trapping” effect along the equator caused by the Earth’s rotation (X. Li and Cho, 1997) (cf. Section 1.2.4)

1. Datasets and Methodologies

1.1 Data

1.1.1 Hourly rain gauges network

Hourly rainfall data come from the Météo-France operational rain gauges network, which provides quality-controlled cumulative records since 1979 over SEF and since approximately 1990 over the two French OTs considered here. Each hourly record is subject to a two-step quality control procedure: a first filter retains only data validated by the automated acquisition algorithm and a second filter retains only data confirmed by the climatologist. Any record failing either criterion is treated as missing. In addition, only stations exhibiting at least one complete consecutive year of available hourly data are retained to ensure a sufficient observational basis for wet spell extraction. We obtain a total of 667 stations over SEF, 100 over REU and 31 over GUI. At each rain gauge, WSs are defined as isolated or consecutive wet hours receiving at least 1 mm of rainfall, following Moron et al. (2025). This threshold indeed avoids dependence on variable lower detection limits across instruments and networks but still capture more than 90% of the total rainfall amount across all each study area. Applying this definition to the full set of available stations yields a total of 1 056 375 WSs over SEF, 303 435 over REU, and 117 550 over GUI. Since most analyses require a sufficient temporal depth to resolve seasonal and interannual variability, a stricter criterion of at least 10 years in SEF and 5 years in OTs of available data is applied for the most part of the analyses presented in this work. This choice reduces the network to 415 stations over SEF (1993-2024), 82 stations over REU (1998-2024), and 19 stations over GUI (1998-2024), retaining 884 662, 266 508 and 92 192 WSs respectively. The spatial distribution of these stations is displayed in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: (a) Map of the mean intensity of wet hours ≥ 1 mm for rain gauges with at least 10 years of available data in SEF. (b) and (c) Same for the two OTs for rain gauges with at least 5 years of data.

Figure 1 shows that the spatial distribution of rain gauges is very dense and quite homogeneous in SEF and REU. In GUI, however, the stations are mainly concentrated along the coastline, although there are still a few rain gauges scattered fairly sparsely inland, but never very far into the interior of the continent. Looking at the average intensity, two main points can be noted to already characterize the specific features of the three study areas: (1) Due to the terrain and its orientation, SE and REU show consistent spatial patterns with high intensities on windward slopes to the moisture fluxes. This is particularly the case for the Cévennes in SEF and the island’s mountainous inland in REU. Conversely, GUI shows a less consistent distribution of intensity due to the topographic homogeneity of this territory. (2) Mean intensities differ significantly from one region to another. SEF records the lowest intensities ($\bar{m} = 3.0$ mm, $sd = 0.4$ mm)⁴, in contrast to REU, where they are the highest, up to 6 mm/h ($\bar{m} = 4.6$ mm) but also the most scattered ($sd = 0.6$ mm). Finally, GUI shows the same range of intensity than over REU ($\bar{m} = 4.6$ mm) but much more homogeneous across the rain gauges network ($sd = 0.2$ mm).

⁴ \bar{m} and sd represents respectively the mean and standard-deviation across each rain gauges network.

1.1.2 Atmospheric products

Atmospheric fields come from ERA5 reanalysis produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts, available at a horizontal resolution of 0.25° on pressure levels and at the surface. ERA5 provides hourly estimates of atmospheric variables, each representing an instantaneous snapshot valid at the corresponding timestamp in Coordinated Universal Time (UTC). Two subsets of ERA5 data are used in this work, differing in their temporal resolution and spatial domain:

- (1) The first subset is extracted at a 6-hourly time step (0, 6, 12 and 18 UTC) and subsequently averaged to daily means. It covers a domain of $80^\circ \times 80^\circ$ centered on each target rain gauge, and includes the following variables: zonal and meridional wind components at 850 hPa ($U850$ and $V850$, in m.s^{-1}) and at 200 hPa ($U200$ and $V200$, in m.s^{-1}); air temperature at 850 hPa ($T850$, in K) and at 200 hPa ($T200$, in K); mean sea level pressure ($MSLP$, in hPa); total column water vapor ($TCWV$, in kg.m^{-2} , equivalent to mm of precipitable water); and two derived dynamical fields at 850 hPa computed from the horizontal wind. Any horizontal wind field can indeed be decomposed into a rotational component, characterized by its relative vorticity ($VOR850$, in s^{-1}), which measures the local spin of the flow and is positive for cyclonic circulation in the northern hemisphere, and a divergent component, characterized by its horizontal divergence ($DIV850$, in s^{-1}), which measures the net outflow of the wind field at a given point and is closely linked to vertical motion (Hawkins and Rosenthal, 1965).
- (2) The second subset is extracted at the hourly time step and covers a domain of $20^\circ \times 20^\circ$ centered on each target station. It is restricted to five variables: convective available potential energy ($CAPE$, in J.kg^{-1}), convective inhibition (CIN , in J.kg^{-1}), and once again $TCWV$, in kg.m^{-2} , U10 and V10 wind components (m.s^{-1}). $CAPE$ measures the maximum buoyant energy available to a lifted air parcel, and is therefore a proxy for the potential intensity of convective updrafts (Moncrieff and M. Miller, 1976), while CIN quantifies the energy barrier that must be overcome before free convection can be triggered. These hourly fields are used for the sub-daily composite analyses described in Section 1.2.3.

1.1.3 Tropical storms and equatorial waves catalogs

Tropical depression data come from the International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IB-TrACS, (Knapp et al., 2010)), which provides the position (latitude and longitude) and intensity of all recorded tropical disturbances at a 6-hourly time step since 1980. Following common practice, only systems that have reached at least tropical storm intensity (i.e., sustained surface wind speeds exceeding approximately 17 m.s^{-1}) are retained, excluding weaker tropical depressions. A cyclonic day is defined as any calendar day during which at least one such system is located within a radius of 1000 km from any station of the OM network under consideration. This horizontal distance threshold is consistent with the typical influence of associated extreme precipitations and with previous studies focusing on TCs-related rainfall in the southwestern Indian Ocean (Cornillault, 2025). The resulting catalog covers the 1980-2024 period over the Indian Ocean basin for REU. The corresponding spatial distribution of TCs trajectories and their relationship to local extreme rainfall exceedances are illustrated in Figure 9.

Sub-seasonal atmospheric variability associated with CCEWs is characterized using a catalog of intraseasonal anomalies provided by the TROPICS team at the National Centre for Meteorological Research (CNRM, Météo-France). This catalog is built by isolating anomalies of several atmospheric fields (here $TCWV$, $U850$ and $V850$) with respect to a climatological annual cycle smoothed with a 90-day low-pass filter. The residual anomaly field is then decomposed into the contributions of individual CCEWs using a time-frequency filtering method described in Section 1.2.4, as well as the four wave modes retained in this study. This catalog is available at a horizontal resolution of 1° and at a 3-hourly time step, subsequently aggregated to daily means for the analyses presented here and in other studies (Latos et al., 2026)

1.2 Methods

1.2.1 Canonical wet spells attribution

Rather than recomputing a new clustering from scratch, the CWSs defined by Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025 are used directly as reference centroids. Each centroid is defined as the mean 24-hourly normalized and

square-rooted rainfall profile of each cluster, as described in the [Introduction](#). Each WS recorded across the three study areas is assigned to the nearest centroid by minimizing the Euclidean distance computed directly in the 24-dimensional space of normalized hourly profiles, following:

$$k^* = \arg \min_{k \in \{1, \dots, 7\}} \sum_{h=1}^{24} (r_h - c_h^{(k)})^2 \quad (1.1)$$

where r_h is the hourly rainfall of the WS at hour h from its onset expressed in the same normalized space as the centroids, and $c_h^{(k)}$ is the corresponding value of centroid k . This attribution is performed independently for each study area (SE, REU, GUI), so that no mixing occurs between networks.

Table 1.1 reports the relative CWSs frequency across the study areas. The distributions are broadly consistent, with CWS#1 systematically dominating (accounting for 52% of all WS in the tropics and between 61 and 63% in the three study areas) followed by CWS#3 and CWS#5. The most notable differences concern the short-intense CWS#2 and CWS#4, which are substantially less frequent in SEF (3% and 1% respectively) and REU (4% and 2%) than in the tropical network (9% and 5%), while GUI shows frequencies closer to this tropical reference for CWS#2 (9%) but remains lower for CWS#4 (3%). Conversely, the long-lasting CWSs #6 and #7 are slightly more represented in REU (4% and 2%) than in SEF (2% and 1%), which seems quite consistent with the role of TCs activity in sustaining long-duration events over the island.

Network	CWS#1	CWS#2	CWS#3	CWS#4	CWS#5	CWS#6	CWS#7
Tropics	52	9	20	5	9	4	1
SE France	63	3	19	1	11	2	1
Réunion	61	4	17	2	10	4	2
French Guiana	63	9	15	3	7	2.5	0.5

Table 1.1: *Relative CWSs frequency (in %) across the tropical network of [Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025](#) and across the three regions considered in this study. Frequencies are computed over the full set of extracted WSs (cf. Section 1.1.1).*

The projection of the seven CWSs in the mean duration-intensity space is shown in Figure 2 for SEF alongside the original tropical centroids for comparison. We can see that the general pattern of the CWSs is well respected: as in the tropical band, CWSs #1, #3, #5, #6, and #7 are fairly well aligned along a straight line where the mean intensity of the centroid increases with duration⁵, with the exception of CWS #7, where this visual relationship deviates slightly. In addition, the remaining CWSs #2 and #4 are clearly identifiable, as they consistently exhibit the highest mean intensity. We also see that the boundary of the group comprising all WSs closely approximates the behavior of CWSs #1 and #3, which is consistent with [Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025](#), given that both together account for more than 80% of the WSs in this case. Furthermore, we can observe that this group averaging all WSs clearly does not allow to distinguish certain types of events, especially whether very long ones like those of CWS #7 or very short and intense ones like those of CWSs #2 and #4.

Compared to tropical CWSs, there is a noticeable common pattern on CWSs of SEF, which are, on average, (1) slightly less intense and (2) slightly longer in duration. This is consistent with a rain gauges network subject to extratropical circulation, whose large-scale dynamics is mainly driven by stratiform frontal systems capable of sustaining more persistent rainfall over time. This zone also differs from the tropics in having lower convective instability (i.e. less CAPE) and lower atmospheric available water amount (i.e. less TCWV), which also contributes to the observed reduction in mean intensity. The systematic detection of such a signal is therefore expected and encouraging from a methodological point of view. It also demonstrates the ability of the CWS framework – even though it is “fixed” – to account for the specific features of various geographical areas where the nature of rainfall events can differ fundamentally. This is quite evident in the intermediate CWSs (notably CWS #3 and #5), which, in the case of the SE, are relatively much longer in duration than the others. Regarding OTs, this observation is also supported, for instance with CWS #7, which is very long and intense on average in REU and much shorter and scarcer in GUI.

⁵Even though this linear relationship remains uncertain due to each within-cluster spread.

Figure 2: Projection of the 7 canonical wet spells (CWSs) according to their respective mean duration (in h) and intensity (in mm). Solid ellipses delineate a ± 1 sd interval around each southeastern France (SEF) CWS centroid (shown with colored points) while dashed ellipses and crosses correspond to the tropical CWSs derived from Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025 and displayed for comparison. The annotation in the lower right indicates the correlation between duration and intensity of WSs, independently of CWSs. This value is identical to that of Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025 and equal to 0.21 in GUI and 0.3 in REU. For comparison, the correlation between duration and total amount is systematically ≥ 0.78 for the three study areas.

Figure 3 plots the cumulative distribution of WSs duration per CWS and per study area, showing first of all that, with the exception of WSs within CWS #7, nearly all events last 12 hours or less. More specifically, in SEF and REU, more than half of the WSs last only one hour, and this proportion exceeds 60% in GUI. When comparing the three study areas with one another, we also observe that, for a given proportion of WSs, their mean duration is consistently shorter in GUI and consistently longer in SEF, with REU sitting between the two. This observation holds true on average across all WSs, but also individually for each CWS, with the exception of CWSs #2 and #4, for which the durations are nearly identical across the three regions. Equally, it is clear that in the case of CWS #7, the differences are more pronounced, and REU exhibits the longest events for a given proportion of WSs.

Once again, the ability to identify these nuances between different territories clearly demonstrates that the conceptual framework of CWS allows (1) for the identification of consistent characteristics of each region – making it an interesting analytical tool for subsequently studying their variability and atmospheric environment – and (2) at least in SEF, to show that CWSs #2 and #4 behave differently from other WSs since they lose their longer mean duration compared to analogous CWSs in the two OTs.

Figure 3: Cumulative fraction of wet spells (WSs) ≥ 1 mm per CWS and for all WSs combined as a function of duration (in h). For each CWS, we plot all the recorded WSs with the thin transparent curves, as well as 50th (dotted lines), 25-75th (solid lines) and 10-90th (dashed lines) percentiles for each study area, i.e. SEF (in blue), Réunion (REU, in red) and French Guiana (GUI, in green).

1.2.2 Dynamic clustering

Since the SEF rain gauges network integrates a wide range of climatological configurations – shaped by geographical parameters such as elevation, distance to the coastline, and exposure to prevailing atmospheric air masses – the contribution of each CWS to the rainfall amount and its seasonal modulation may vary substantially from one station to another. To address this, a spatial clustering of SEF stations is performed in order to define a set of sub-regional areas that are internally consistent from the point of view of the CWSs seasonal contribution. The clustering is based on the mean annual cycle of the 30-day running contribution of each CWS to the local rainfall amount. For each station, this yields a matrix of 7 CWS \times 365 running monthly windows, which serves as the input variable. A k -means algorithm is then applied to partition the stations into k groups by minimizing the total within-cluster inertia:

$$\arg \min_{\mathbf{S}} \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{\mathbf{x}_j \in S_i} \|\mathbf{x}_j - \boldsymbol{\mu}_i\|^2 \quad (1.2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ is the centroid of cluster S_i and \mathbf{x}_j is the input vector of station j . To reduce the dimensionality of the input space and filter noisy variance, the clustering is performed in the reduced EOF space of the input matrix, keeping the leading five eigenvectors that collectively explain 90% of the total variance.

The optimal number of clusters k is selected by combining several complementary criteria. The classifiability index (CI) (Michelangeli, Vautard, and Legras, 1995; Moron, Gourand, and Taylor, 2016) is computed for each value of k between 2 and 10 by running 1000 random initializations of the k -means algorithm and measuring the mean similarity of the resulting centroids across runs. The Davies-Bouldin index, the Gap statistic, and the Silhouette coefficient are also computed as additional measures of cluster compactness and separation. The CI reaches its highest value at $k = 3$ and decreases consistently from $k = 4$ onward, which is consistent with the Davies-Bouldin and Gap indices that both point to $k = 3$ as the optimal solution. Even though the Silhouette coefficient favors $k = 2$, we choose the 3-cluster solution as it provides a more informative distinction while remaining parsimonious. The resulting regionalization is displayed in Figure 5 and the corresponding mean annual cycles of CWSs contribution per cluster are shown in Figure 6.

1.2.3 Composites

Composite analyses are used to characterize the mean atmospheric environment associated with the occurrence of each CWS. For each occurrence recorded at a given station, the corresponding ERA5 grid point is identified as the nearest neighbor in terms of great-circle distance. The composite is then computed over a spatial window centered on this grid point, covering $80^\circ \times 80^\circ$ for the daily fields and $20^\circ \times 20^\circ$ for the hourly fields. This approach means that each occurrence contributes a spatially recentered atmospheric snapshot, so that the composite retains the recurring signal targeted at the station, highlighting the system most strongly connected to each CWS, while averaging out the station-to-station geographical variability (including relief for instance). Formally, the composite of a variable X for CWS k at spatial offset $(\delta i, \delta j)$ from the target grid point and temporal lag ℓ relative to the onset day d_0 can be expressed as follow:

$$\bar{X}^{(k)}(\delta i, \delta j, \ell) = \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_{n=1}^{N_k} X(i_n + \delta i, j_n + \delta j, d_0^{(n)} + \ell) \quad (1.3)$$

where N_k is the number of occurrences of CWS k , (i_n, j_n) is the ERA5 grid point closest to station n , and $d_0^{(n)}$ is the onset day of the n -th occurrence. Concerning daily composites, lags range from $\ell = -3$ to $\ell = +1$ days relative to d_0 while regarding hourly composites, lags range from -24 h to $+24$ h. Note that in the case of daily composites, d_0 is defined as the calendar day during which the majority (i.e. $> 50\%$) of the WS cumulative rainfall is recorded; if more than half of the total amount falls on the following calendar day, d_0 is shifted forward by one day accordingly, to ensure that the composite is properly centered on the wettest part of the event. Two types of anomalies are computed, depending on the temporal scale considered:

- For the daily composites, anomalies are expressed relative to a local dry climatology, defined independently for each station and each calendar day as the mean atmospheric state on days without recorded rainfall (0 mm). This reference ensures that the composite anomaly reflects the real departure from a locally dry background, rather than a simple seasonal mean that would potentially conflate the meteorological signal with the mean annual cycle. All lags, including the most distant ones ($\ell = -3$ days), are therefore referenced to the same dry climatological baseline fixed at d_0 .
- For the hourly composites of CAPE, CIN, and TCWV, a lag-to-lag anomaly formulation is used instead. Each value at lag ℓ is expressed as the difference relative to the value at the immediately preceding lag $\ell - 1$, except at $\ell = -24$ h, which is referenced to the local dry climatology as defined directly above. This formulation highlights the progressive evolution of the atmospheric environment in the hours leading up to and following CWS onset. It is particularly suited for characterizing the buildup and release of convective instability at the sub-daily time scale, as illustrated in Figure 14.

It should be noted that, for reasons of computational cost, anomalies are computed and resampled using a maximum of 5 000 occurrences ($n = \text{station} \times \text{days}$ or $\text{station} \times \text{hours}$) falling within each CWS whenever this threshold is exceeded. This does not, in principle, alter the final result, since the mean and standard deviation still already very stable starting at $n = 1000$. We also mention that all hourly composites are expressed in local solar time (LST) rather than UTC, which appear more convenient for the interpretation, with respective offsets of UTC+1 for SEF (winter time applied regardless of the day of the year), UTC+4 for REU, and UTC-3 for GUI.

1.2.4 Intraseasonal anomalies extraction

CCEWs are coherent atmospheric structures resulting from the trapping of wave energy along the equator by the Earth's rotation and the equatorial β -effect (Matsumo, 1966; G. N. Kiladis et al., 2009). Their dispersion and structural characteristics are described by the shallow-water equations projected onto an equatorial β -plane, which yields a discrete set of normal modes identifiable in the zonal wavenumber-frequency space. In particular, CCEWs modulate deep convection and rainfall at subseasonal timescales of 2 to 60 days, and are therefore a primary source of intraseasonal predictability in the tropics (G. N. Kiladis et al., 2009; Vitart and Robertson, 2018; Moron and Robertson, 2021). However, CCEWs are rarely detectable in raw atmospheric fields or even in their anomalies (Peyrille, Roehrig, and Sanogo, 2023). To address this, the CCEWs filtering methodology used in this work follows the approach implemented in the MISVA platform (Monitoring of IntraSeasonal VAriability, <https://misva.aeris-data.fr>), a joint research and operational

tool developed by the TROPICS team at CNRM in collaboration with forecasting services in West Africa and OTs. Intraseasonal anomalies are first computed by subtracting a smoothed climatological annual cycle from the raw atmospheric fields, where the annual cycle is estimated as the long-term daily mean low-pass filtered with a 90-day running window. A 2D Fourier transform is performed in time and space on the residual anomaly to project the parameter into the wave number-frequency space and then decomposed into the contributions of individual CCEW modes, as documented in [M. Wheeler and G. N. Kiladis, 1999](#). The extracted variables are TCWV (in kg m^{-2}), U850 and V850 (in m s^{-1}), which are among the most informative. We retain four wave modes in this work, listed in decreasing order of their typical period:

- the **Madden-Julian Oscillation (MJO)**, 30-90 days, eastward propagation at $\sim 5 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$);
- **Equatorial Rossby waves (ER)**, 15-20 days, westward propagation at $\sim 5 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$);
- **Kelvin waves** (4-15 days, eastward propagation at $\sim 15 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$);
- **Easterly waves (TD (*tropical disturbances*))**, 2-10 days, westward propagation at $\sim 8 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$) and **Mixed Rossby-Gravity waves (MRG)**, 2-10 days, westward phase velocity at $\sim 25 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$). These two modes contributions are stacked into a single category given the similarity of their spectral signatures.

The resulting catalog, provided at a horizontal resolution of 1° and a 3-hourly time step, is subsequently aggregated to daily means for the composites analyses, presented in Section [2.2.2](#).

1.2.5 Harmonic analysis

The diurnal cycle of CWS frequency and intensity is characterized using a standard harmonic decomposition of the mean hourly distribution of each rainfall quantity over a 24-hour period, based on [Verma et al., 2026](#). For a discrete hourly signal $P(t)$ of period $T = 24 \text{ h}$, the first harmonic reconstruction is:

$$P_1(t) = a_1 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T}\right) + b_1 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T}\right) \quad (1.4)$$

where the coefficients a_1 and b_1 are estimated by integration of $P(t)$ against the sinusoidal basis functions. The amplitude $A_1 = \sqrt{a_1^2 + b_1^2}$ and phase $\Phi_1 = \arctan(b_1/a_1)$ give respectively the maximum departure from the mean and its timing. We retain only the first harmonic, capturing the dominant 24-hour periodicity. The decomposition is applied to the mean diurnal rainfall distribution attributed to the onset hour of each CWS event. The diurnal modulation strength is expressed by a contribution index:

$$\mathcal{C}_k = \frac{\sum_{t: P_1(t) > 0} \bar{P}(t) - \sum_{t: P_1(t) < 0} \bar{P}(t)}{\sum_{t=0}^{23} \bar{P}(t)} \times 100 \quad (1.5)$$

where $\bar{P}(t)$ is the mean observed rainfall at hour t . Values near 100% indicate that onset rainfall fall almost entirely in the positive phase of the diurnal cycle while values toward 0% reflect a near-uniform distribution across the day. Results are shown across the 3 three study areas for each CWS in [Figure 15](#).

1.2.6 Trend detection

Long-term changes in aggregated WS characteristics – including mean and maximum hourly intensity, frequency of wet hours, and mean duration – are assessed over SE using 10-year running means, restricted to the 96 stations with at least 30 years of available data. This approach allows the multi-decadal signal, expected to reflect either natural modes of variability or the anthropogenic forcing, to emerge more clearly. The statistical significance of this time series is assessed using a non-parametric Mann-Kendall monotonic trend test at the two-sided 95% level. This test is distribution-free and therefore well suited to the non-Gaussian character of rainfall distributions. To contextualize the observed trends, all significant slopes are normalized relative to the theoretical CC scaling of approximately $7\% \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, applied to the observed European warming of $+1.45^\circ\text{C}$ over the same period (cf. [Figure 18](#), Copernicus European State of the Climate report, 2025). In [Section 3](#), each slope is thus expressed as a fraction of this CC expectation, allowing a direct assessment of super-CC or sub-CC behavior across significant CWS characteristics.

1.2.7 Analytical workflow overview

Figure 4 summarizes the full set of analysis steps carried out in the framework of this thesis, that is to say in a general manner both for the three study areas and for the seven CWSs. Nevertheless, it is clear that it is impossible to present, interpret, and discuss all of these aspects within this work for lack of space, since this would imply at minimum $3 \times 7 = 21$ typical situations to describe for each potential variable (or even more when separating cyclonic versus non-cyclonic occurrences, or different sub-regions in SEF for instance). Thus, in the following **Results** and **Discussion** sections, we have in certain cases chosen to draw from all these results only a single territory or relevant examples of several CWSs in order to illustrate the analytical potential of this approach. Indeed, from a conceptual point of view, the predominant relevance of the CWS lens is to be able to summarize in a synthetic manner numerous aspects of rainfall variability both in space and time. Consequently, the selected examples try to show in the best possible way that the CWSs allow to retrieve *a posteriori* characteristics that define them, despite the fact that these characteristics are not included in their initial definition (large-scale dynamical conditions, local thermodynamic conditions, CCEWs activity, etc.). This framework is not insignificant, since the level of information contained by the CWSs indeed enables them to illustrate the three-way interplay between (1) duration, (2) spatial scale and (3) intensity, something that the daily timescale does not truly allow, to the extent that the duration of WSs is by definition aggregated over 24 hours in this case.

Figure 4: Schematic block diagram of the main steps implemented in this study for the methodology and the analysis through the CWSs framework for the different study areas.

2. Results

2.1 Regional and seasonal fingerprint of canonical wet spells

2.1.1 Regionalization of southeastern France rain gauge network

The results of the SEF regionalization are displayed in Figure 5. From the clustering of rain gauges based on the seasonal contribution of CWSs to the local 30-day cumulative amount, we can identify three distinct subregions (whose acronyms are explained in the caption of Figure 5). Furthermore, the following interpretation is supplemented by the results of Figure 6, which shows the mean CWSs annual cycles for each of the subregions obtained from the classification, namely : (1) Toulouse basin, southern Alps, western coastal Corsica (TBSA-WCC) subregion encompasses the broader Toulouse Basin and part of the Pyrenees mountain range to the west, as well as the southern part of the Alps and the western coast of Corsica to the east of the study area. This subregion has the highest stations mean elevation (566 m), even though the latter vary a lot between the rain gauges; (2) Cévennes, Languedoc, Roussillon, Alpes-Maritimes, northern Corsica (CLRAM-NC) covers most of the east/southeast-facing mountain foothills in the study area and records the lowest mean elevation (484 m). The Cévennes are the best example of this configuration, but the subregion also includes Roussillon, the foothills of the Alpes-Maritimes mountain range, and *Castagniccia*, a mountainous and fertile micro-region in northeastern Corsica; (3) Rhône valley, Mediterranean coastline, inland Corsica (RVMC-IC) is the subregion with the highest number of rain gauges and thus a medium mean elevation (506 m). It includes the entire metropolitan area coastline, extends up along the Rhône Valley, and also encompasses mountainous inland Corsica.

Figure 5: Location map of Météo-France rain gauges network across SEF over 1979-2025 period, superimposed on elevation (shaded in grey, in m). Clusters of rain gauges are based on the local contribution of each CWS to the total rainfall amount over 30-day running windows for stations with at least 10 years of available data. The bottom inset shows the cumulative density distribution of each rain gauge cluster as a function of elevation. The resulting 3 subregions are respectively : (1) TBSA-WCC (in red), (2) CLRAM-NC (in blue) and (3) RVMC-IC (in green). Note that remaining unused stations are plotted in black.

TBSA-WCC is characterized by a predominance of contributions from CWSs #1 and #3, which also happen to be the least influenced by the annual cycle. CWSs #2 and #4, which are the only ones that occur exclusively in summer and early fall, are also slightly less represented there than in the other two subregions. Furthermore, CWS #7, which exhibits extremely pronounced seasonality in CLRAM-NC, contributes very minimally to the seasonal amount. Moreover, RVMC-IC corresponds more closely to the average situation among the three subregions, particularly in the case of the most frequent CWSs, i.e., #1, #3, and #5. Similarly, CWS #7 remains fairly marginal, unlike what is observed in the CLRAM-NC subregion. The latter shows a significantly higher contribution from CWS #7 in both spring and fall, a pattern that is also seen to a lesser extent with CWS #6, which, by definition, is close to it in term of mean duration and intensity. CWSs #1 and #3 logically account for a smaller proportion there compared to the other subregions, except during summer when the proportion balances out. In addition, we can notice that regardless of the three subregions, CWS #2 and CWS #4 exhibit particularly similar behaviors and contributions across the year, except in RVMC-IC, which is the warmest on average during summer and where they still a bit more frequent.

Figure 6: Mean annual cycles (solid colored curves) of the contribution (in %) of each CWS to the total rainfall amount over 30-day running windows per regional cluster in SEF. Note that corresponding colored dashed lines represent a ± 1 sd confidence interval for each configuration. Moreover, solid black lines, along with their grey-shaded intervals, show the spatial mean of the three regions for each given CWS (and thus remain constant from one region to another but do differ among CWSs).

This regionalization suggests that the intraseasonal distribution of the rainfall amount, as well as the types of CWSs that shape it, not only depend on elevation but also on more characteristic geographic and topographic parameters such as relief, distance from the coastline, hillslope orientation, among others. The fact that CLRAM-NC rain gauges are systematically located where the relief gradient is highest on the east/southeast-facing foothills and that they record a typical marker of CWS #7 (which is the longest one) not found in the other two subregions supports this finding. Similarly, the clustering results also show that geographically distinct areas (e.g., the Toulouse basin versus the Southern Alps) can exhibit comparable patterns regarding the contribution of each CWS to the seasonal amount. Finally, the fact that CWSs #2 and #4 exhibit seasonality that is both very different from the other CWSs and fairly invariant across subregions suggests that they are more scattered and therefore do not necessarily depend on a specific geographic or synoptic configuration to occur.

2.1.2 Seasonality and atmospheric scenarios of wet spells in French overseas territories

In the same way, Figure 7 displays the mean annual cycles of each CWS relative contribution to the 30-day rolling total amount across the two OTs. The first observation is that seasonal differences among CWSs are much less pronounced within the same OT than in SE. For both REU and GUI, the peak contribution of the CWSs coincides with the seasonal contribution of total rainfall and, consequently, with the rainy season.

For GUI, the peak of the wet season falls between late March and early August, but the contribution phase of each CWS does not necessarily align exactly with this timeline. For example, short CWSs (CWS #1 and #2) reach their peak contribution relatively late in the rainy season and continue to contribute significantly to the total amount during the dry season. Conversely, as their duration increases, CWSs occur earlier in the rainy season. This is particularly the case for CWSs #6 and #7, whose peak ends around late June and whose contribution is nearly zero during the dry season. If we turn to REU, the pattern is even less distinct between CWSs. Overall, the most frequent CWSs (i.e., CWSs #1, #3 and #5) are also the least influenced by seasonality, with a contribution that remains significant during the austral winter, aligning particularly well with the annual variation in total rainfall. CWS #2 and #4 appear to be more strongly influenced by the annual cycle and are virtually absent during the dry season. Furthermore, the largest contribution comes from the longest WSs attributed to CWS #7, which are also highly variable during the cyclone season ($sd \approx \pm 15\%$), suggesting that this CWS contains a significant proportion of TCs occurrences.

Figure 7: Mean annual cycles (solid colored curves) and associated ± 1 sd confidence intervals (colored shadings) of the contribution (in %, left y-axis) of each CWS to the total amount over 30-day running windows for REU (in blue) and GUI (in red). The dotted lines correspond to the mean annual cycle of the total fractional rain (in %, right y-axis) over the same running intervals. We plot in the bottom right the number of rain gauges with at least 5 years of data available each year over 1998-2025 for both OTs.

Despite the fact that CWSs seasonal patterns are very similar, their very different nature in term of mean duration and intensity lead us to examine the atmospheric conditions associated with their lifetime, from initiation through to the day following the event. Figure 8 illustrates the progression of three composite time sequences in OTs, computed using only non-cyclonic WSs. This allows us to characterize the systems involved, as well as their large-scale environment⁶:

- **CWS #4 in REU:** This first time sequence shows an extratropical disturbance breaking away from the mid-latitude track and drifting northeastward during the rainy season. Several days before $d0$, the trade winds are already weakening rapidly, and the low-pressure system is moving northward toward REU from the southwest. The wind then shifts to the northwest, and on $d-1$, an oblique structure

⁶We draw here on some elements from the work on classifying weather patterns over REU done by forecasters at Météo-France Interregional Division for the Indian Ocean, especially regarding the sensible weather and amounts associated with WSs occurrences (even though our description still rely on the composites obtained here). Concerning the not shown composites, they appear much more homogeneous between CWSs in SEF (except regarding the spatial scale of their anomalies) with a low pressure to the west causing moist hot air to be advected by a SW to SE flow depending on lags and CWSs. In REU, the conditions between CWSs allows for comparisons with the two cases presented: CWS #2 looks like the attenuated #4 and CWSs #5 or #6 also look like the attenuated #7. Finally, CWSs #1 and #3 show distinct weaker and more zonal structures.

resembling a front forms just upstream of the island. On d_0 , as the front passes, winds shift to the southwest within a cooler air mass, accompanied by a potentially highly unstable frontal band that is often associated with significant thunderstorm activity. If this situation occurs in summer (which is the case here), the frontal track is generally less pronounced than in winter, but the associated moist air mass is more persistent, although it remains here quite localized. Precipitation first arrives from the north and then from the southwest as the front passes. This situation causes sustained heavy rainfall over the foothills, sometimes justifying the issuance of an orange alert level. This weather pattern can be summarized as a *summer convective cold front associated with a mid-latitude disturbance*.

Figure 8: Mean-standardized composite anomalies of precipitable water (TCWV, colors), meridional and zonal wind at 850 hPa (U_{850} and V_{850} , vectors) and mean sea level pressure (MSLP, contours) atmospheric fields for non-cyclonic day occurrences (identified via IBTrACS data beyond a 1000 km radius from each OT station) associated with CWSs during their respective seasonal period of occurrence (December-May in REU vs March-August in GUI) over 1998-2024. Anomalies are displayed only when they are significant at the two-sided 5% threshold. Significance is assessed by randomly resampling non-rainy, in season days (same amount as the number of non-cyclonic days) for 500 simulations and taking the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the resulting bootstrap distribution. Positive MSLP anomalies correspond to red contours, and negative anomalies to blue contours. For wind, vectors are displayed when at least one of the two components is significant. Only CWS #4 and CWS #7 are shown for REU (1st two rows) and CWS #1 for GUI 3rd row while each column correspond to a specific daily lag from $d-3$ to $d+1$ compared to WSs onset.

- **CWS #7 in REU:** The middle time sequence shows a completely different synoptic configuration, with the gradual formation of a weak tropical low-pressure system to the east of the island from $d-3$ to $d-2$, which remains quite stationary in space. At the same time, the Mascarene high is moving rapidly south of the island toward the same direction. This motion intensifies the cyclonic vortex of the low-pressure system at the target, and a large-scale positive TCWV anomaly develops. On day_0 , the Mascarene high moves northward, which tightens the pressure gradient at the target and progressively blocks the flow to the northeast. The low-pressure system can then no longer move eastward, intensifies, and leads to significant and persistent rainfall amounts on the eastern flank and in the mountainous inland of REU. Although mid-latitude circulation clearly plays a role in triggering CWS #7 in this case, it might also be associated with the crossing of one or more CCEWs due to the rapid onset of the large-scale moisture anomaly. Then, we can characterize this weather pattern as a *tropical low locked and enhanced by the subtropical Mascarene ridge*.

- **CWS #1 in GUI:** The last time sequence shows the typical scenario of what occurs in GUI. The trade wind flow is prominent on a large scale beforehand, as along a zonal moisture anomaly well aligned with the latitude of the target and a marked dry anomaly to the south. From $d-3$ to $d-1$, the moisture anomaly intensifies (but remains half as strong as in REU) and spreads westward until it reaches the target on $d0$. At the same time, the flow becomes distinctly convergent upstream of the target and slightly cyclonic behind the target, due to the tentative arrival of a low-pressure system upstream of the target. This behavior suggests the propagation of one or more CCEWs, not only advecting moisture from the east (e.g. ER) but also creating a weak cyclonic vortex behind the target associated with a cold anomaly at 850 hPa (e.g. MRG+TD). We will deliberately remain broad in our definition of this weather pattern as *transient westward-propagating wave(s)*.

More broadly, we can note that WSs in REU are much more likely to be linked to interactions with extratropical circulation due to its geographic position, as in the two cases shown. This is an important point from a forecasting perspective, as it means that CWSs in this case tend to be modulated by large-scale forcings throughout the rainy season. Beyond the peripheral influences presented here, WSs can also be triggered by an incursion of the mid-latitude jet stream, causing a well-known forcing in the upper troposphere (Morel et al., 2014). Furthermore, the patterns are more similar among CWSs that occur in GUI. The structures are actually much more zonal, with a fairly clear propagation of a positive TCWV anomaly. This dynamic suggests the role of one or more CCEWs in triggering most CWSs in GUI. While these composites can not provide further insights, the contribution of CCEWs to CWSs occurrence is discussed in Section 2.2.2.

2.2 Large-scale drivers of wet spells in French overseas territories

2.2.1 Tropical cyclones contribution to local extremes exceedance in Réunion

As identified in previous studies, it may be relevant to distinguish TCs occurrences versus no TCs occurrences when the contribution to the total amount and the frequency of those systems become substantial in the study area (Cornillault et al., 2024). In this work, we did this operation for REU and analyzed the role of TCs on extreme rainfall occurrences by examining them through the CWSs framework. First of all, Figure 9 allows us to examine the trajectories of TCs within the Indian Ocean basin and to identify those that affect REU island. To define a cyclonic event, we use a great circle distance criterion previously employed in the literature (Englehart and Douglas, 2001). While the distance itself may vary depending on the chosen threshold of selectivity and the study areas, we have decided to use a 1000-km criterion here, as previously applied in other studies on REU (Cornillault, 2025). This approach can also be justified quite simply by showing that the mean conditional probability of exceeding a local extreme is virtually zero at a 1000 km distance from the network ($\bar{P} < 5\%$ for the 95th percentile (among all days), $\bar{P} < 0.5\%$ for the 99th percentile), which, in other words, illustrates that almost all local TCs events are included by using this criterion.

In addition, we see that the formation of TCs affecting REU generally begins in the same latitude zone around 15°S, but across a wide band of longitudes ranging from approximately 50°E to 100°E. On average, and in the majority of cases, TCs propagate westward, generally following the climatological track of trade winds between December and March (i.e. almost purely zonal easterlies) before turning south over the Mascarene region, from Rodrigues Island in the east to the Mozambique channel and the African coastline in the west. The 15 most extreme TCs (i.e. exceeding the local 99th percentile over at least 10% of the network on a given day) exhibit three fairly consistent common features: (1) the systems pass in close proximity to REU, (2) they slow down and/or follow quite chaotic (and thus stagnant) paths within the 1000-km radius around the island, and (3) they have the longest trajectories, suggesting that these are the most persistent (and thus the largest) systems and that they impact REU at an already high stage of maturity.

When we cross-reference TCs with CWSs occurrences, we end up finding that TCs occur predominantly within CWS #7. Specifically, TCs account for between 30% and 80% of the total rainfall amount per station in this CWS and represent between 5% and 30% of rainy days there. Regarding other CWSs, the TCs contribution is approximately about 10 to 30% and fairly homogeneous, with a sensible higher frequency and contribution within the remaining most intense CWSs (CWS #2, #4, and #6). We can also describe the role of TCs differently by focusing not on the local contribution but on CWSs themselves. In this case, the

predominance of CWS #7 over the others remains well established, with a 30% probability that a TC fall within CWS #7 when among rainy days. By contrast, this proportion is only 4% for CWS #1 and remains three times lower in the case of CWS #6 and CWS #4. Similarly, it can be said that when a TC occurs, it will account, among rainy days, for 55% of the total amount of CWS #7, compared to less than 20% in all other CWSs. By way of comparison, these proportions are already quite high relative to the contribution of TCs in other tropical (Cornillault, 2025) or subtropical areas (Moron, Barbero, and Robertson, 2015).

Figure 9: (a) Map of all tropical storm (TS) trajectories (transparent grey lines) across the Indian Ocean basin over 1980-2025 and of all the TS trajectories (transparent steel blue lines) detected within a radius ≤ 1000 km from a station with at least 5 years of available data in REU. TS trajectories that triggered an extreme (\geq local 99th percentile among all days) over at least 10% of the rain gauge network are plotted with thick blue lines. We also plot mean (thick red curve) and median (dashed red curve) TS trajectories those reported at 1000km or less from a REU rain gauge, as well as a 1000 km-diameter circle centered on the barycenter of REU network. (b) Upper panel : Map of TCs (daily occurrences) contribution (in %) to the local total amount over 1998-2025 per CWS. Lower panel : Map of the local TCs frequency (in %) among days ≥ 1 mm. The fractions in the title indicate respectively the contribution and the frequency of TCs within each CWSs among rainy days. (c) Diagram of the mean probability (in %) to reach a local extreme (either $\geq 95^{\text{th}}$ (in black) or $\geq 99^{\text{th}}$ (in red) percentile) against distance (in km) from TC center during cyclonic days.

Thus, it might be relevant to look at the atmospheric environment associated with TCs falling into CWS #7, both to check the coherence of the system and to characterize it physically. Figure 10 illustrates composite anomalies related to TCs occurrences. We observe that the conditions are highly consistent with studies documenting TCs cases over the Indian Ocean. In detail, we see that the system is associated with a strong large-scale low-pressure anomaly, supported at the center by a very high positive TCWV anomaly ($+15 \text{ kg/m}^2$), and whose intrusion occurs from the northwest. 850 hPa wind speed anomalies are not particularly high, especially around the system, which is consistent with previous findings by Cornillault, 2025 showing that the most impactful TCs tend to slow down near the island. Furthermore, the winds support a convergence anomaly and advect cyclonic vorticity from northeastern to the western sectors. Besides, the warm core is clearly visible in both the lower pressure levels and at higher altitude, indicating the tropical source of the system and is associated with a strong divergence anomaly at 200 hPa. All these characteristics support TCs energy as long as it is not inhibited by continental friction (Wong and Chan, 2006). Finally, dry anomalies are also observed around the system at 850 hPa, which is consistent with the sensibility of moisture variability to strong and sustained convection at the center (Wu et al., 2015).

Figure 10: (a) Mean-standardized composite anomalies of TCWV (colors), U850 and V850 (vectors) and MSLP (contours) of cyclonic day occurrences (identified via IBTrACS data within a 1000 km radius from REU stations) associated with CWS #7 rainfall events during the December-May TC season over 1998-2024. Significance at the two-sided 95% threshold is assessed the same way as in Figure 8. Same principle for divergence (DIV850, colors) and vorticity (VOR850, contours) anomalies at 850 hPa. (c) Same for temperature (T850, colors) and wind (vectors) anomalies at 850 hPa and (d) at 200 hPa.

2.2.2 The role of equatorial waves on canonical wet spells occurrence

CCEWs represent a second type of large-scale driver explaining rainfall variability in the OTs, and more generally within the tropical belt. In particular, on a daily to sub-daily timescale, the modulation of rainfall amount is primarily linked to the activity of short-wavelength waves (i.e., Kelvin and MRG+TD). On a weekly timescale, the maximum contribution is rather associated with ER, whereas beyond 20 days, only the MJO signal is detectable (Schlueter et al., 2019). In this study, we choose to examine intraseasonal anomalies on a daily timescale in order to distinguish faster-scale variability modes. This option appears particularly relevant given that the active phases of slow modes tend to provide an environment favorable to the development of faster-scale waves activity, and vice versa.

Figures 11 and 12 combine the CWS framework with that of total intraseasonal moisture anomalies and the contribution of the four modes of variability described in Section 1.2.4. An initial interesting observation is that CWSs distinguish much more active regimes than others, in terms of (1) the number of CCEWs involved, (2) the intensity of their activity, and (3) their spatial extent. Almost systematically, the occurrence of a CWS also corresponds to the passage of one (or more) CCEWs over the target at d0. This result supports the idea that convective activity is favored by the passage of a wave and that this effect is enhanced when the positive phases of the “fast” and “slow” modes overlap, without addressing for the moment the conditional role of exclusive CCEWs configurations on each CWS (see Figure 13). In detail, we observe that the OTs exhibit more active wave regimes for the longest and most intense CWSs, particularly CWSs #4, #6, and #7. These CWSs are also associated with a spatially large-scale positive MJO anomaly, which is not the case for the shorter CWSs. This result supports the idea that the MJO actively modulates cyclonic activity in the Indian Ocean during its early stages of development⁷, which is consistent with the idea that short-lived CWSs are less connected to large-scale circulation.

It is also interesting to note that the GUI exhibits highly zonal structures, with a fairly clear and consistent signal over ERs, which are characterized by meridional anomalies and whose symmetry is sometimes clearly evident, as seen in CWS #4. It can also be noted that although the total anomalies are weaker on CWS #1, they are also very large, suggesting a significant role of the wet season in modulating this CWS. Regarding REU, the anomalies are nearly twice as high at the target during the occurrence of each CWS. In CWS #2 and #4, we also find oblique structures reminiscent of the composites in Figure 8. This projection is not fundamentally contradictory given that the island’s subtropical position facilitates interactions with mid-latitudes. In particular, interaction is possible during intense jet stream undulation, resulting tropopause forcing, or the refraction of mid-latitude Rossby waves (MLRs) toward the tropics (Webster and Holton, 1982).

⁷M. C. Wheeler and Hendon, 2004 show that MJO activity can be divided into an 8-phase propagating cycle from East Africa to the central tropical Pacific, with the MJO reaching its peak maturity over the maritime continent before decaying. This segmentation is notably characterized by positive zonal wind anomalies and negative OLR anomalies in the lower layers.

Figure 11: Time sequences from $d-3$ to $d+1$ of mean-standardized total composite intraseasonal anomalies of TCWV (colors) and TCWV anomalies due to the contribution of CCEWs (contours) for each CWS in Réunion. Contributions are identified through a wave number/frequency filtering explained in Section 1.2.4. Only wet waves phases are displayed and the relative latitude is cropped at -8.5° due to the geographical location of REU compared to the south margin of the tropical zone. Contours are set in ascending order at 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 kg/m^2 . We apply a factor $(\cos(\text{lat})/40)^4$ to highlight tropical circulation.

Figure 12: Same as Figure 11 for French Guiana. Note that here latitude is set from -15° to $+15^\circ$.

In our case, this can also manifest as the passage of a front, which remains fairly rare at subtropical latitudes but nevertheless accounts for a significant fraction of precipitation across the tropics as a whole (10–30%) and especially in the Indian Ocean (50%) (Catto and Pfahl, 2013). In addition, a link has been established between Kelvin waves and MLRs (Straub and G. Kiladis, 2003). Indeed, it is possible that MLRs project into the spectral domain of Kelvin waves, or even trigger their initiation.

Extending on this, Figure 13 highlights exclusive CCEW configurations most likely to be associated with WSs occurrence. We can separate two modulation effects : (1) as the number of simultaneously active CCEWs increases, so does rainfall probability, and (2) configurations with no or with only one active CCEW are generally unfavorable for a WS occurrence. A threshold effect thus becomes apparent starting with two waves co-located over the target on the same day, beyond which the probability modulation increases with the number of waves. We also observe that this pattern is nearly identical between the two OTs, with REU simply being modulated approximately 1.5 times more in amplitude than GUI. These results are consistent with other studies regarding the role of CCEWs in modulating heavy rainfall (Peyrille, Roehrig, and Sanogo, 2023). Here we see that these effects are actually more general in nature since they are also found across the entire distribution and not just beyond a given percentile. Besides, if we decompose this modulation for each CWS in REU, it is clear that the previous pattern change. First, CWS #1 interacts very little with CCEWs, regardless of their number. Furthermore, the configurations are much more selective in GUI than in REU. Especially, we observe that if a single wave is present, the environment seems rather increasingly unfavorable for long CWSs (#6 and #7) occurrence. In contrast, we observe that the four-CCEWs configuration is often significant for this long-lasting CWSs. Nevertheless, shorter CWSs (#2, #3, #4) are less influenced by any particular type of configuration (almost all configurations are significant), but still appear just as likely to trigger when only a single CCEW is active, what is not detected when all WSs are aggregated. As mentioned earlier, this effect may also result from a more pronounced interaction of these CWSs with mid-latitudes circulation. Another point is that our criterion for defining CCEWs activity here is based solely on daily amounts and not on OLR plus 850 hPa vorticity, as in other studies (Cornillault, 2025).

Figure 13: Mean probability modulation $\Delta P_{WS}(\text{wave})$ of all WSs occurrence according to CCEWs exclusive configurations for GUI (a), REU (b) and REU per CWS (c). We base on a criterion of ≥ 0.5 sd from the climatology of the IMERG daily rainfall over 1998-2021 to define "active" CCEWs phases. The probability modulation is quantified through the the following expression: $\Delta P_{WS}(\text{wave}) = \frac{P_{WS}(\text{wave}) - P_{WS}(\text{all})}{P_{WS}(\text{all})}$. Opaque bars topped with a star indicate cases that are 95% significant (unlike the transparent bars), assessed by randomly resampling 1000 times the same number of configuration and comparing the observed modulation to the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the obtained bootstrap distribution.

3. Discussion

3.1 Sub-daily triggering mechanisms between the 3 study areas

3.1.1 Hourly scenarios at the target location: the role of thermodynamic processes

Beyond large-scale forcings linked to the synoptic environment and (extra)tropical circulation in its broadest sense, it is also recognized that rainfall variability is governed by sub-daily timescale mechanisms, particularly certain thermodynamic processes (Yang and Slingo, 2001) that, by definition, interact with the diurnal cycle as we will see in Section 3.1.2 (Subrahmanyam, kumar, and Babu, 2015). This observation is especially observed within the tropics, even though, in reality, the spatiotemporal scales of various environments (whether favorable or not) tend to overlap. However, in practice, some studies distinguish between purely "dynamic" and purely "thermodynamic" regimes to improve the understanding of WSs onset from a process perspective (Nesbitt and Zipser, 2003). While this framework may be relevant, it is essential to note that this distinction does not necessarily have to occur. In fact, it is the contributions of the various physical mechanisms that are more likely to vary from one WS to another, while the underlying causes of rainfall remain fundamentally the same (Trenberth, Dai, et al., 2003).

Indeed, the occurrence of any WS implies the potential for a parcel of moist air to rise. In practical terms, this means that, at the time of the WS occurrence, there must be (1) available water vapor, (2) potential energy, and (3) the removal or reduction of the resistance to uplift. As shown in Figure 14, we can see that these conditions are effectively met for the three study areas. Specifically, for all CWSs and all regions, the onset is characterized with a positive TCWV anomaly, as well as a positive CAPE anomaly. Equally, the corresponding inhibition anomaly is negative most of the time, or decreasing several hours before the onset if it is not the case. In fact, we can see that this latter case mainly concerns CWSs #2 and #4, which are very short and very intense and associated with hourly extremes, in both REU and SEF. One might assume, as has already been explained (Shevchenko, Hohenegger, and Schmitt, 2023), that their occurrence is accompanied by this "pressure cooker" effect, implying that the positive CIN anomaly allows for the accumulation of more energy and potential instability prior to the onset. Basically, the CIN erodes progressively in two possible ways: (1) due to diurnal heating until the air parcel in the lower layers reaches its free convection level by becoming warmer than its surrounding environment, (2) or through dynamic forcing such as advection of warm and moist air in the lower layers, advection of cold air at altitude, CCEW crossing, among others.

Despite this common foundation, there are still some fairly notable differences between CWSs and among the three study areas. Typically, TCWV anomalies have a similar magnitude but are consistently more persistent in GUI. This is consistent with the equatorial context and the resulting near-permanent convergence in the lower layers, which maintains a very high reservoir of available moisture at all times. In other words, moisture replenishes quickly in the GUI, unlike in REU and SEF, where moisture anomalies are more transient. Furthermore, we observe that CIN anomalies show little variation between CWSs in GUI, where, once again, the environment maintains a consistently low inhibition level, facilitating the onset of CWSs under the same conditions. Conversely, in subtropical regions such as REU or temperate Mediterranean regions such as SEF, CIN is more variable depending on the season and synoptic conditions, allowing certain CWSs to trigger by overcoming inhibition more effectively than others. This is clearly evident in the case of CWS #2 and #4 in SEF, which really stand out from the others by occurring under a positive CIN anomaly that is much higher than the others. In REU, these are, in fact, the only two to exhibit this behavior. We also see that CWS #2 and #4 have a very high positive CAPE anomaly compared to the others, but that it manifests at different timescales depending on the region. Typically in SEF, instability arrives very quickly and very strongly ($+150 \text{ kg/m}^2$) and dissipates at a similar rate between 12 hours before and 12 hours after the event, whereas in REU, CAPE rises and falls more slowly on either side of the onset, with ultimately relatively little amplitude ($+50 \text{ kg/m}^2$).

This is not as trivial as one might imagine, since it is clear that rainfall intensity profiles for a given CWS are virtually identical from one region to another. CWS #7 may be an exception in GUI, where it appears to be shorter in duration than in the other two regions, but this is also consistently the rarest case. Thus, thermodynamic conditions can vary significantly from one region to another, ultimately resulting in an event of the same duration and intensity (M. Li et al., 2022).

Figure 14: The 3 columns on the left show time series of lag-to-lag anomalies for CAPE, CIN, and TCW, computed at each lag relative to the previous one, except at -24h which is referenced to the local dry climatology. Anomalies are composited from -24h to +24h relative to the onset of each CWS occurrence at a given station, computed on a $20^\circ \times 20^\circ$ grid centered on the target location and plotted as the spatial mean over a $3^\circ \times 3^\circ$ central subspace. Each lag is displayed only if at least one grid point within this subregion is statistically significant. Note that the background is shaded in blue for a positive anomaly and in red in the opposite case. The rightmost column shows the mean hourly intensity composited around the onset of each CWS occurrence, averaged stations with either 5 (OTs) or 10 (SEF) years of data and all WSs belonging to each CWS. We start 2 hours before t_0 and set these values to zero by construction, as t_0 is defined as the 1st hour of a dry-to-wet transition. After the end of each wet spell, the contribution of that event is set to zero, so the mean amount is progressively diluted toward zero as duration increase and thus, as more events have ended.

3.1.2 Diurnal modulation of wet spells frequency and intensity

As we introduced in Section 3.1.1, the diurnal cycle drives the factors controlling the local thermodynamic profile and thus determines when updrafts can occur. By definition, the effect of the diurnal cycle is more pronounced when the mean temperature is higher, that is to say with little seasonal modulation within the tropics (still more in REU than in GUI), and mainly during boreal summer and early fall in SEF. Theoretically, this influence is also more pronounced in the case of short CWSs, whose behavior is much less dependent on large-scale circulation (Moron, Barbero, Fowler, et al., 2021). It is indeed one of the recurring modes of variability that can trigger diurnal heating and potentially enable convection if CAPE, CIN, and TCWV follow a favorable profile. Furthermore, the diurnal cycle tends to sustain a recurring inversion of breeze systems, particularly in the tropics where (1) the thermal contrast between the continent and the ocean is particularly pronounced and (2) the day-to-night duration ratio is much more constant than at extratropical latitudes (Yang and Slingo, 2001). Thus, sea breezes develop during the day, with the flow oriented toward the warmer continent, sustaining updrafts and convection. At night, the flow

system reverses because the thermal inertia of the continent makes it cool more rapidly. Sea breezes then weaken until they reverse into land breezes, which can fuel marine or coastal convection (Baldysz et al., 2023).

Figure 15 examines these aspects, focusing specifically on the frequency of the start time for each CWS, since the relative frequency of all hours may be meaningful for short WSs (1-2 hours) but may become more difficult to interpret for WSs that span a certain number of hours (particularly those exceeding 6 hours). We observe that CWSs #2 and #4 are generally the most modulated compared to the others, with a clearly diurnal convection peak localized in the afternoon for all three regions. This result is consistent with their very short and very intense nature, thus making them, in absolute terms, more akin to convective phenomena. However, we can note some differences regarding them between the three study areas in terms of their timing. Initiation is earliest in REU, with a peak at 2 pm for CWS #4 and at 3 pm for CWS #2 and a frequency anomaly that becomes negative after 7 pm, whereas in GUI this timing is shifted by about 1 hour later. In SEF, the frequency peak occurs at the same time as in GUI but extends later into the evening, typically until 9 pm for CWS #4 and 10 pm for CWS #2. This slight systematic delay in the most purely convective events has already been discussed by Chaboureaud et al., 2004, explaining that these events often have less available moisture and a more persistent CIN level than others prior to the onset of the event.

Figure 15: (a) Mean-standardized anomaly of the relative frequency (in %) of onset hours (originating from dry hours) for each CWS and each study area. Anomalies are plotted by means of a gaussian filter whose width depends on the number of available events $\sigma = 200/N_{onset}$ capped between 1h ($N_{onset} \geq 200$) and 3h (even if $N_{onset} \leq 66$). Note that the background is shaded in blue for a positive frequency anomaly and in red in the opposite case. (b) Mean diurnal contribution (in %) derived from the positive/negative phase ratio of the 1st harmonic of the mean total rainfall, attributed to the corresponding onset hour for each CWS and each study area (colored dotted curves). The black dashed line represents the spatial mean of this contribution across the 3 regions. 95% confidence intervals are computed by randomly reshuffling the local contribution of each CWS across 1000 simulations and taking the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the corresponding bootstrap distribution. Each mean contribution is computed over more than 150 events (all wet spells originating from a transition from another CWS are excluded). Note that figures within the legend show the mean diurnal contribution for each region (all CWS combined) as well as the overall spatial mean across all regions.

We also see that the other short but less intense CWSs (CWSs #1 and #3) display a significant diurnal modulation although less pronounced in amplitude, often quite well aligned with that of their two very intense analogs (#2 and #4). This clearly shows that the shortest events, even those contributing little to the total amount, are by nature more modulated by the diurnal cycle than longer CWSs (that are therefore related to a larger spatio-temporal scale). This is also what we can very well observe for CWSs #5, #6 and #7 in SEF which have an almost flat diurnal cycle, also due to their seasonality which shows a very marked summer minimum beyond the predominant influence of their spatial scale. This observation is less true in REU, where we see that CWS #5 and #6 show a small diurnal convection peak and CWS #7 records a small nocturnal convection peak between 8 pm and 1 am. In GUI, this phenomenon is even more pronounced with an entirely nocturnal phase for CWSs #6 and #7, particularly marked for the latter, with a peak at the end of the night around 4 am. This refers to other previous work on the diurnal cycle in the tropics and the superposition of these two convection cycles in equatorial territories (Anselmo, Schumacher, and Machado, 2020; Natoli and Maloney, 2023), obviously less marked in REU. The most likely hypothesis to explain this, once again, refers to land breezes that recycle ocean moisture at the coast during the night when the flow reverses in the lower layers and maintains the wet updraft above the ocean, particularly in parallel with the dominant flow of trade winds. This mechanism creates a convergence front that boosts the ascendance until the early morning (Yang and Slingo, 2001).

Using the methodology of Verma et al., 2026, we can, to some extent, calculate a form of contribution from the diurnal cycle to the sub-daily distribution of the hourly rainfall amount. Here, we take up this logic by breaking down the hourly amounts according to the occurrence of the seven CWSs. In addition, we assign here the total amount of each WS to its triggering time so as not to mix up information related to their duration, which also seems to be the most relevant concerning the interpretation. Moreover, working as Verma et al., 2026 on the distribution of hourly amount can be relevant in the case where a separation is operated between purely "dynamic" versus "thermodynamic" regimes defined from atmospheric fields, as is the case in the works mentioned. Regarding our study, we find interesting the idea of basing this approach solely on the CWSs framework (thus on the mean intensity/duration of WSs) but not on the associated conditions. This choice allows us to (1) re-evaluate the robustness of the clustering, (2) add an additional level of information (the triggering of the seven different types of WSs) and (3) to discuss this contribution by comparing the results between the three study areas and with results that are based on a more explicit categorization of rainy regimes from the behavior of the atmosphere.

The results of this analysis thus show that, on average, the contribution of the diurnal cycle to the triggering of WSs is significantly greater in OTs (about 20%) than in SEF (about 12%), even though the overall pattern between CWSs remains similar. Indeed, short and intense CWSs (#2 and #4) show a greater contribution of the diurnal to their onsets than the others in the case of SEF and REU (around 30% for #2 and 25% for #4). In the case of CWS #2, this result is also observed in GUI but the contribution on CWS #4 is lower (about 10%). More broadly, GUI stands out with long CWSs that are most controlled at initiation by the diurnal cycle, all things being equal, with about 30% for CWS #6 and 60% for CWS #7. For comparison in SEF, the same two CWSs both record a contribution below 5%. These results differ significantly from those of Verma et al., 2026, who found an mean contribution close to 50% in their purely "thermodynamic" regime and a contribution around 10% in their purely "dynamic" regime. This can be explained by the fact that the latter concerns yet another tropical territory (i.e. India, western Gats), but also by the difference between the two approaches. On the one hand, Verma et al., 2026 define their two exogenously regimes from a large-scale variable (u850 and v850 on the Somali jet) and look at how hourly amounts are distributed on average over the course of the day. On the other hand, our work is based on an endogenous basis to the rainy system itself from the intrinsic properties of CWS and allows us to see when each CWS is most likely to trigger during the day, regardless of the current atmospheric circulation. This gives a complementary approach showing that (1) the distinction between "dynamic" vs "thermodynamic" regimes is not perfect, especially depending on the study area, (2) the triggering of WSs seems to be related in a smaller proportion to the diurnal cycle than the distribution of the rain itself and (3) the CWSs can be transposed to other methodologies without assuming the atmospheric situation involved in their occurrence.

In line with these results, Figure 16 illustrates how the frequency of triggering each CWS varies depending on its percentile in terms of total amount, regardless of its duration. Beyond the differences between the

long and short CWSs already highlighted in Figure 15, this points out several notable aspects. For instance, an "extreme" CWS does not necessarily correspond to an increase in the anomaly on its peak frequency. This is notably what we observe in the case of CWSs #2, #3, and #4 where increasing the percentile does not necessarily change the amplitude of the positive frequency anomaly of the onset. For other CWSs, such as #1, the amplitude increases positively during the frequency peak. In addition, the onset phase can also be shifted. This is a point that we clearly see in the case of CWS #4 in SEF, with a peak around 3 pm for the 50th percentile, which shifts towards the end of the afternoon for the 90th percentile (6 pm), or even in the evening for the 99th percentile (8 pm). More generally, it is also found that the 99th percentile is often discarded from the pattern of other percentiles, especially for long CWSs which are already less modulated by the diurnal cycle than the others.

Figure 16: Same as Figure 15.a but for a wide percentile range (50th-99th) for each CWS (columns) and each study area (rows). Here we only plot the curves when the configuration totalize ≥ 48 events (which corresponds to a minimum frequency of 2 events per hour in the theoretical case of equiprobability) and we plot the cycle with dashed lines when $N_{onset} < 240$. Note that the column headers show the 50th and 99th percentile values of total WS amount for each CWS and each study area. For French Guiana, blue vectors show the 10-m wind anomaly (relative to the daily mean during the same WS) at the nearest grid point to each onset station whose CWS local contribution (cf. Figure 17) is \geq to the 50th percentile of the mean contribution of this CWS on the rain gauges network. This anomaly is averaged over all CWSs ($\geq 50^{\text{th}}$ percentile) onset hours (if $N_{onset} \geq 240$). Vector orientation follows standard geographical conventions (up=north, right=east, down=south, left=west), analogous to a flattened wind rose projected onto the time axis.

Consequently, these results support the fact that, regardless of the CWS (except for #2), the occurrence of an extreme is less related to the diurnal cycle than to large-scale circulation (Barlow et al., 2019). The exception of CWS #2 nuances things by highlighting that for very brief and very intense events (and therefore very localized), which are typically stormy convective systems, the occurrence of an extreme remains related to the diurnal cycle in the same proportions as the other percentiles of this WS type, regardless of the study area. This is an important distinction in terms of predictability since we know that these systems are *a priori* the most complex to be represented by weather forecasting models and *a forciori* climate models, especially for those without explicit resolution of convection (Prein et al., 2015). However, it is clear that the extremes attributed to CWS #2 present a major challenge for civil society, as they can cause flash floods due to urban runoff in artificialized cities and cause significant damages to infrastructures (Fowler, Ali, et al., 2021). Our results indeed illustrate that these events could be associated with amounts of about 50 to 80 mm over 1 hour on average for cases above the 99.5th percentile. For comparison, the maximum warning level defined by Météo-France in an issue area of a lowland department is associated with ≥ 80 mm amounts over a full day ⁸. However, in the most extreme cases of CWS #2, we expect about the same order of magnitude

⁸Météo-France official website. 2026. URL: vigilance.meteofrance.fr

occurring over a period 24 times shorter, i.e. an extremely intense event even if the daily amount does not necessarily correspond to an exceptional accumulation or to exceeding a certain percentile level.

Finally, Verma et al., 2026 also link their regimes to local breezes systems, showing that in the case of a purely "thermodynamic" event, the local low-level jet weakens and the breezes systems strengthen with the continent-sea temperature gradient. Figure 16 illustrates this aspect by projecting the mean hourly 10m-wind anomalies for GUI and is to be compared with Figure 17, both for interpretation and to highlight the limits of the analysis. We indeed settle these anomalies from the fraction of stations where each CWS contributes the most, to avoid mixing different spatial influences too much. This method is not perfect, because obviously in REU the coast is circular and therefore the directions can theoretically compensate each other. That's why we don't show the results for REU or SEF that typically are very blurred and display several inversions within the day. For GUI, since the alignment along the coastline is quite the same between all rain gauges, the results appears much more relevant. In fact, in GUI, we see that the 10m-wind anomalies systematically reverse direction between 10 am and noon, shifting from N-NE to S-SW. For each CWS, this reversal coincides with the beginning or end of their respective onset peak. Short CWSs associated with diurnal convection are therefore clearly linked to a sea breeze, while long CWSs are more associated with a nocturnal land breeze. The maximum recorded speed anomalies are typically around 3.6 m/s (approximately 13 km/h), which seems very consistent with the values normally measured for surface breezes across equatorial areas (S. Miller et al., 2003).

These results complement those in Figure 17, which show, for instance, that long CWSs contribute mainly to the total amount along the coast and not inland, unlike CWS #2, where the contribution is minimal on the coast and maximal inland. In REU, although breezes cannot be interpreted without clearly separating the portions of the coastline into the four geographic directions, the local contributions of CWSs are consistent with (1) what is expected theoretically and (2) what is observed on composites. Short CWSs are confined to the coasts and foothills, while long CWSs have a larger spatial extent, notably CWS #7, which primarily affects the mountainous inland rain gauges. Furthermore, CWS #4, associated with the crossing of a stormy cold front arriving from the west, clearly shows maximum contributions over this part of the island.

Figure 17: Upper panel: Local contribution of each CWS to the total amount (in %) in REU for rain gauges with at least 5 years of available data. Mean and standard deviation of each map (i.e. across all stations) are indicated in their corresponding title. Lower panel: Same for GUI.

3.2 Issues in detecting rainfall intensification at different timescales

3.2.1 Daily vs sub-daily interannual variability of aggregated wet spells characteristics

Another aspect that can influence the variability of WSs can be played at the interannual timescale. Indeed, different modes of variability from regional to global scale are known as being an integral part of the climate system and are widely studied such as the North Atlantic Oscillation in the extratropical North Atlantic (Strommen and Palmer, 2018) or El Niño in the tropical South Pacific (Janicot, Moron, and Fontaine, 1996). Beyond these so-called natural modes of variability, it is now established that the ongoing AGW, induced by human activities⁹ has led to a rise in mean global temperature of about +1.2°C since 1920, of which +1°C since the 1970s. This monotonic increase in temperature leads to multiple implications on all the

⁹IPCC, 2026. URL : <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/sixth-assessment-report-cycle/>

spatio-temporal scales of the climate system, which are often apprehended by means of modelling in the more or less long term and according to different scenarios. Even though it is now clearly established that the frequency and intensity of heat waves have significantly increased under the effect of AGW (Fischer and Knutti, 2015), this signal is much less obvious when it comes to rainfall, especially depending on the timescale used to detect it (Barbero et al., 2017). Theoretically, the CC relationship predicts an increase of +7% in water vapor in the air per additional °K, but the rainfall response is usually difficult to connect to this law (Allen and Ingram, 2002), or even contradictory (Lenderink and Meijgaard, 2008), notably due to the involvement of multiscale dynamic and thermodynamic processes allowing *in fine* to a rainy event occurrence.

Indeed, many steps are involved in the occurrence of WSs and there is no basis for assuming *a priori* (1) whether and (2) how their characteristics are likely to change over a given region. Once again, theoretically, the two most obvious changes assumed concern frequency (because it has a better signal-to-noise ratio (Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025)) and mean intensity (because it is directly related to warming and therefore the CC law involving wetter air). In SEF, the situation is even more complicated to analyze because the WSs vary greatly from one region and season to another, as we were able to show within the Section 2.1.1, due to specific geographical parameters, types of situation that generate them, and associated weather conditions. On a seasonal to an annual timescale, the models predict rather a decrease in the mean total amount in the southern half of France, combined with an increase in the northern half, noting that these trends exhibit strong seasonal modulations (Haruna et al., 2026). However, previous work shows that these changes are not significant, or even invisible in the observations, even on characteristics such as the frequency and intensity as long as these studies use daily data. At the hourly timescale, very few studies use observations to document the interannual evolution of these characteristics, due to a lack of temporal depth. In this case, we focus on SEF whose rain gauges network allows us to use almost a hundred stations over a 32 years period. We first proceed to a comparison of the interannual variability between the hourly and the daily timescales in the frequency and mean intensity of all WSs combined, before looking at how these characteristics evolve within each CWS.

Figure 18 displays the results of the confrontation between these two time steps. In the following, anomalies are expressed as a percentage change relative to the first reference decade (1993–2002), with the total slope over the entire 1993-2024 period given in parentheses. There is notably a significant increase in the mean intensity of rainy hours of about +4% (+0.1mm/h) combined with a decrease in the frequency of rainy hours of about -35% (-4.5%). These two changes are not detected at all at the daily timescale, as they do not show any significant trend, especially regarding the frequency of rainy days, which remains perfectly constant over the study period. We can see in these results an obvious compensatory effect between, on the one hand, a rarefaction of WSs occurrence combined with an increase in their mean intensity. This observation confirms what models project about the regional evolution of the Mediterranean climate, notably showing a lengthening of dry periods (Lesk and Mankin, 2026). In addition, we observe in the figure that the modification of these two components works in parallel with a decrease in the mean duration of WSs of about -6% (-0.1h). All the variations of these three characteristics are therefore consistent and indeed not visible from the daily timescale since they depend on duration, which by definition can only be characterized from the hourly timescale. By aggregating the hours between them, we therefore mixed the frequency and intensity of WSs, which, at least in this case of SEF, seems detrimental for detecting the intensification of rainfall under the effect of AGW.

In detail, we can also assume that the intensification of WSs will not record the same amplitude depending on whether we look at an extreme or not. This aspect is quite well documented in the literature, especially for short and intense events that often exhibit higher intensification than what is expected by the CC law, namely a "super CC" effect (Lenderink, Barbero, et al., 2017). Behind that, some authors also showed that this effect is also highly variable depending on the regional climatic characteristics and on the seasonality (Obarein and Lee, 2025). The third panel in Figure 18 explores this aspect, projecting the normalized trend with respect to a CC effect calibrated on European warming, of mean intensity for different percentiles, for rainy hours versus rainy days. In the same way as before, we observe that the increase in intensity is systematically detected on the hourly timescale regardless of the percentile, and that as the latter is high, the intensification effect is also. Typically, percentiles below the hourly 95th percentile record an increase in mean intensity that is lower than what is predicted by the CC law, while 95th and especially 99th

percentiles follow it much better, if not perfectly in this second case. The hourly 99.9th percentile shows a super CC, consistent with boosted intensification for the most intense WSs, especially those associated with short durations (Fowler, Lenderink, et al., 2021). In other words, at the hourly timescale, we observe a consistent progression of the average intensification of WSs as we move towards extremes. Conversely, only one configuration out of the five shows an increase in mean intensity at the daily timescale, but it is actually the most intense, i.e. the daily 99.9th percentile. The other daily percentiles show either non-significant trends (75th and 99th) or a significant decrease in mean intensity of rainy days (90th and 95th). It can be assumed that the increase of the 99.9th percentile for the most intense rainy days concerns almost exclusively very long events whose duration, on average, approaches the daily timescale, which explains this alignment with the CC law compared to other percentiles. Nevertheless, these results clearly show that the hourly timescale provides an additional level of information regarding the intensification of rainfall compared to the daily timescale, and that this change is reinforced (and therefore more likely to be detected) towards extreme percentiles in a very consistent way.

Figure 18: (a) Running mean over 10-year moving windows of the rate of change (in %) in the intensity of rainy days (black curve) versus the mean rate of change in the intensity of rainy hours (red curve) calculated for SEF rain gauges network using the 96 rain gauges with at least 30 years of available data over 1993-2024. 95% two-sided confidence interval (transparent envelopes) is computed using 2.5% and 97.5% percentiles of the bootstrap distribution, which is obtained by randomly selecting 50% of the available rain gauges from each 10-year segment across 500 simulations. A non-parametric Mann-Kendall trend test is then applied to the mean series to test its significance at a two-sided 95% level. This result is indicated in the subplot title, as well as the total slope (in physical units) computed over the entire period. Note that the time axis (x-axis) is centered on the period 1998–2020 to account for the offset caused by calculating the time series over 10-year segments. The first and last segments therefore cover the decades 1993–2002 and 2015–2024, respectively. (b) Same as (a), but for the rate of change in frequency of rainy days and rainy hours (in %), as well as for the rate of change in mean duration (green curve) of all wet spells. (c) Linear regressions of running mean time series over 10-year segments of the mean intensity of rainy days and rainy hours across various percentiles (75th, 90th, 95th, 99th, 99.9th). Each regression is normalized relative to the theoretical increase of 7%/°K in the water vapor content of the air, as established by the Clausius-Clapeyron (CC) law, and scaled relative to the increase in the mean temperature of Europe over 1993-2024, estimated at +1.45°C according to the Copernicus report on the European state of climate (URL: <https://climate.copernicus.eu/ESOTC-2025-report.pdf>), i.e., a 10% increase in the water vapor content of the air. Each regression line is colored according to a scale of the observed CC effect. Non-significant configurations are plotted in gray and the theoretical increase that would perfectly follow the CC law is shown through the black dotted line.

3.2.2 Assessing shifts of wet spells duration and intensity in a warming climate

By keeping the same logic but breaking down the WSs into CWSs, as shown in Figure 19, a new level of information can be accessed. This gives the opportunity to see whether each CWS is affected or not and equivalently or not by the previously described modifications. It is thus observed that the increase in

intensity affects all CWSs overall, whether it is mean intensity, peak hours intensity or maximum intensity. Nevertheless, it is clear that the most intense CWSs (#2 #4 and #7) are affected by a more pronounced increase than the other CWSs, whether it is simply more systematic over the percentile range or more intense altogether. Typically, we see that the 99.5th percentile of the mean intensity of these three CWSs is intensified according to a super CC effect, and this is also true as early as 95th percentile for CWS #7. More broadly, it is also observed that the increase in intensity is more common on short CWSs (#1 and #3) than on the long ones (#5 and #6) and that #1 and #3 are rather below the relationship provided for by the CC law. Regarding the duration of CWSs, configurations are less often significant but nevertheless concern all CWSs whose mean duration decreases over at least one percentile. In particular, CWSs #2 and #6 are the most affected with a more systematic decrease in their mean duration. In other words, these results illustrate once again that the most intense WSs are more likely to record a signal on the increase of rainfall intensity. Furthermore, the decreasing signal in duration and frequency (not shown) appear as a more invariant characteristic independently of the CWSs, with the exception of CWS #2, which shows both a more explicit decrease in duration and a less obvious decrease in frequency than other CWSs.

Figure 19: (a) Summary table showing the trend in the mean intensity (in mm/h) of each CWS for several percentiles (from P50 to P99.5), calculated using 10-year running mean among stations in SEF with at least 30 years of available data. Colored cells indicate situations that are statistically significant at the 95% bilateral threshold according to the Mann-Kendall test described in Figure 9, while cells are displayed in gray otherwise. Within each significant box, the total slope (in physical units), calculated over 1993-2024, is displayed. The colors of the boxes correspond to the same CC-scaling as the one described in Figure 18. (b), (c) and (d) Same as (a) but for peak hours intensity (in mm/h), maximum intensity (in mm/h) and duration (in h). Note that concerning peak hours intensity, we computed a mean intensity not over the entire duration of the event, but only during the hours with the heaviest rainfall amount. These hours are defined manually based on the average intensity profiles of each CWS. Hence we get, respectively: CWS1=h1; CWS2=h1; CWS3=h1+h2; CWS4=h1+h2; CWS5=h2+h3; CWS6=h2+h3=h4; CWS7=h7+h8+h9.

These results suggest that the detected increase in the mean (and maximum) intensity of most CWSs effectively constrains their duration and frequency. In other words, all the characteristics of WSs are modified simultaneously: for most CWSs, especially at their extreme percentiles, it rains (1) more intensely (on average and instantly), (2) for shorter periods and (3) less frequently. The interplay of these transformations is in line with other results whose intuition seems correct to us, notably the numerous studies modelling the response of the water cycle under AGW by the end of the century (Pendergrass and Hartmann, 2014).

Conclusion

This work reuses a clustering method of rainfall events used by [Moron, Cornillault, et al., 2025](#) on 1123 rain gauges across the tropical belt into seven centroids (CWSs). Here, we reassign the WSs of SEF, REU and GUI to each CWS, characterized by a specific mean duration and intensity. Due to the intermittence of rainfall, the CWSs harness the near statistical independence between the intensity and frequency of rainfall amounts insofar as less than 0.5% of WSs have a duration lower than 24 hours. The reassignment of WSs shows consistency in the pattern of the seven CWSs, which also manages to transcribe geographic specificities of each territory, notably a slight decrease in mean intensity and a slight increase in mean duration of CWSs outside the tropical zone. Significant differences are also observed between the two OTs, with a class of very long and very intense WSs in REU while the most durable WSs are much shorter on average in GUI, and above all much more homogeneous than in the other two territories. More broadly, this clustering also shows that relative CWSs frequencies are quite similar between the three study areas and allows to deduce many elements that are not part of their initial definition (duration, mean and maximum intensity, spatial extent, modulation of CCEWs regimes, among others).

The regionalization of rain gauges based on the mean annual cycle of the seasonal contribution of the CWSs to the total amount in SEF allows us to distinguish three sub-regions whose behavior differs between most of the CWSs: (1) TBSA-WCC for the Toulouse basin and the Southern Alps, (2) CLRAM-NC for the Cevennes band and the Alpes-Maritimes and (3) RVMC-IC for the Rhône valley and the metropolitan coastline. The first sub-region is distinguished by a more pronounced contribution of short, frequent and low-intense CWSs (#1 and #3). The second by a very pronounced contribution of long and intense CWSs (#6 and #7) occurring almost exclusively in spring and principally in fall. The third sub-region is close to the mean contributions over the entire study area and the short and very intense CWSs (#2 and #4) stand out with an exclusively summer contribution that is fairly invariant between the three sub-regions.

The CWSs show a marked seasonality but much less contrasted between them in both OTs, notably due to the wet season. Composite analyses of atmospheric scenarios of each CWS rather show a large-scale control associated with their respective occurrences. In REU, cyclonic cases, mostly associated with the longest and most intense CWS (#7) contribute between 10 and 50% to the local total amount and account for 5% to 30% of rainy days. Non-cyclonic cases in REU illustrate obvious interactions of rainy systems with mid-latitude circulation, unlike in GUI where WSs are mainly associated with zonal propagation of different CCEWs, whose influence is less obvious to characterize in REU. In any case, their overlapping clearly tends to favor the occurrence of both WSs and extremes, regardless of CWSs. We also observe more active regimes than others depending on the CWS, with notably no particularly favorable configuration in the case of the least intense CWS (#1) and often favorable configurations on the most intense CWSs (#2, #4, #6 and #7).

The local conditions associated with the occurrence of CWSs are quite invariant. Both a positive CAPE and TCWV anomaly and a negative or weakened CIN anomaly are required. However, the temporal scales of these anomalies differ significantly between the three study areas and between the CWSs in SEF. Indeed, their variation highlights that CWSs #2 and #4 are those whose thermodynamic profile amplitude varies the fastest outside the tropical zone, typically between -6h and +6h compared to CWS onset. They are also associated with a diurnal convection peak occurring in the afternoon or early evening depending on the study area and the chosen percentile. The longest CWSs appear logically less driven by the diurnal cycle, except in GUI where they exhibit a nocturnal convection peak that perfectly aligns with the inversion dynamics of local land/sea breezes, thus occurring preferentially on the coast.

The trend analysis compares the hourly versus the daily timescales, highlighting that the daily timescale undergoes a compensation effect of a significant increase in the mean intensity of rainy hours and a significant decrease in their frequency, also combined with a decrease in the mean duration of WSs. These rainfall shifts in SEF make it possible (1) to corroborate the expected intensification of WSs through climate models or observations from previous studies ([Ribes et al., 2019](#)) and (2) to show that while some studies show that the detection of the intensification of extreme rainfall is sometimes better detected at the daily timescale

(Barbero et al., 2017), this does not allow to contextualize this intensification using other characteristics, in particular duration and frequency. The hourly time step and *a forciori* the extreme percentiles appear in this case to be the most suitable for detecting their modifications under the effect of the AGW.

Our work is part of long-term research seeking to characterize rainfall variability in the OTs and in the Mediterranean area, by confronting the influence of very different modes of spatio-temporal variability. Furthermore, this study also supports the idea that the hourly timescale is the keystone to properly document the intrinsic properties of rainfall events, to better anticipate risks associated with their occurrence. Our approach also points out the fact that it may be insightful to explore both the predictability and the impact of CWSs, in order to quantify their respective contributions to flood hazards.

In conclusion, we would point out that while some authors emphasize the intrinsic unpredictability of natural systems due to their sensitivity to initial conditions (Koutsoyiannis, 2010), our approach shows that this randomness coexists with recurrent structures (e.g. the CWSs). The latter, though individually governed by the full complexity of the climate system, exhibit a form of exploitable statistical recurrency that actually reveals a three-way relationship (between duration, spatial extent and intensity) of rainfall spatio-temporal variability, since they allow to identify, *a posteriori*, distinct and stable statistical properties or atmospheric conditions at the cluster scale. Therefore, even though a tiny variation can theoretically shift an event from its attractor to another, ergodicity allows us to assume that the CWSs observed in the past cover the space of possible states of the current system, and that their recurrence could be reasonably extrapolated for future climate projections (Palmer and Hagedorn, 2006; Faranda, Messori, and Yiou, 2020; Faranda, Vrac, et al., 2020). Obviously, these projections requires a quantification of uncertainty, directly linked to the time horizon and the spatial scale associated to the prediction. Our work clearly shows that, in one way or another, the CWSs capture a *signal*, while the residual *noise* remains quantifiable through the associated probability distributions. In other words, the *signal/noise* dichotomy seems remains both an interesting and reliable conceptual approach, typically on the scale of a few decades (i.e. the predominant analytical scale of climate science *a priori*), as well as a lever for practical applications such as estimating the occurrence probability of extreme rainfall events, thus helping to a more effective management of hydro-meteorological risks for civil society.

Bibliography

- Allen, Myles and William Ingram (Oct. 2002). “Constraints on Future Changes in Climate and the Hydrologic Cycle”. In: *Nature* 419, pp. 224–32. DOI: [10.1038/nature01092](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature01092).
- Anselmo, Evandro M., Courtney Schumacher, and Luiz A. T. Machado (Sept. 2020). “The Amazonian Low-Level Jet and Its Connection to Convective Cloud Propagation and Evolution”. EN. In: *Monthly Weather Review* 148.10, pp. 4083–4099. ISSN: 1520-0493, 0027-0644. DOI: [10.1175/MWR-D-19-0414.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-19-0414.1). URL: <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/mwre/148/10/mwrD190414.xml> (visited on 04/24/2026).
- AR6 Synthesis Report (2026). *AR6 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2023 — IPCC*. URL: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/sixth-assessment-report-cycle/> (visited on 06/04/2026).
- Baldysz, Zofia et al. (Dec. 2023). “Diurnal variability of atmospheric water vapour, precipitation and cloud top temperature across the global tropics derived from satellite observations and GNSS technique”. In: *Climate Dynamics* 62. DOI: [10.1007/s00382-023-07005-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-023-07005-0).
- Barbero, Renaud et al. (Jan. 2017). “Is the intensification of precipitation extremes with global warming better detected at hourly than daily resolutions?” In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 44. DOI: [10.1002/2016GL071917](https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL071917).
- Barlow, Mathew et al. (Dec. 2019). “North American extreme precipitation events and related large-scale meteorological patterns: a review of statistical methods, dynamics, modeling, and trends”. In: *Climate Dynamics* 53, pp. 1–41. DOI: [10.1007/s00382-019-04958-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-019-04958-z).
- Biasutti, Michela and Sandra Yuter (Sept. 2013). “Observed frequency and intensity of tropical precipitation from instantaneous estimates”. In: *Journal of Geophysical Research (Atmospheres)* 118, pp. 9534–9551. DOI: [10.1002/jgrd.50694](https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrd.50694).
- Boudevillain, Brice et al. (July 2011). “The Cévennes-Vivarais Mediterranean Hydrometeorological Observatory Database”. In: *Water Resources Research - WATER RESOUR RES* 47. DOI: [10.1029/2010WR010353](https://doi.org/10.1029/2010WR010353).
- Catto, J. L. and S. Pfahl (2013). “The importance of fronts for extreme precipitation”. en. In: *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 118.19, pp. 10, 791–10, 801. ISSN: 2169-8996. DOI: [10.1002/jgrd.50852](https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrd.50852). URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/jgrd.50852> (visited on 06/04/2026).
- Chaboureaud, J.-P et al. (Oct. 2004). “Role of stability and moisture on the diurnal cycle of convection over land”. In: *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* 130, pp. 3105–3117. DOI: [10.1256/qj.03.132](https://doi.org/10.1256/qj.03.132).
- Chetrit, Tom (Sept. 2025). *Extreme rainfall variability in the French Mediterranean (1945-2022)*. Tech. rep. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.35835.17446](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35835.17446).
- Cornillault, Erwan (Sept. 2025). “Événements extrêmes sur les territoires outre-mer : mécanismes physiques et développement d’outils de prévision aux échelles synoptique et saisonnière”. These de doctorat. Université de Toulouse (2023-....) URL: <https://theses.fr/2025TLSES142> (visited on 04/21/2026).
- Cornillault, Erwan et al. (Aug. 2024). “Large-Scale Drivers of Tropical Extreme Precipitation Events: The Example of French Overseas Territories”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 51. DOI: [10.1029/2024GL108770](https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL108770).
- Cusack, Stephen and Tyler Cox (Sept. 2025). “Brief Communication: Drivers of the recent warming of the Mediterranean Sea, and its implications for hail risk”. In: *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences* 25, pp. 2963–2972. DOI: [10.5194/nhess-25-2963-2025](https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-25-2963-2025).
- Dangers Météorologiques Pluie Inondation | VIGILANCE METEO FRANCE* (2026). URL: <https://vigilance.meteofrance.fr/fr/dangers-meteorologiques-pluie-inondation> (visited on 06/04/2026).
- Dunkerley, David (Dec. 2018). “How does sub-hourly rainfall intermittency bias the climatology of hourly and daily rainfalls? Examples from arid and wet tropical Australia”. In: *International Journal of Climatology* 39. DOI: [10.1002/joc.5961](https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.5961).
- Englehart, Phil J. and Arthur V. Douglas (2001). “The role of eastern North Pacific tropical storms in the rainfall climatology of western Mexico”. en. In: *International Journal of Climatology* 21.11, pp. 1357–1370. ISSN: 1097-0088. DOI: [10.1002/joc.637](https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.637). URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/joc.637> (visited on 06/04/2026).
- Faranda, Davide, Gabriele Messori, and Pascal Yiou (Feb. 2020). “Diagnosing concurrent drivers of weather extremes: application to warm and cold days in North America”. In: *Climate Dynamics* 54. DOI: [10.1007/s00382-019-05106-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-019-05106-3).
- Faranda, Davide, Mathieu Vrac, et al. (Aug. 2020). “Changes in Future Synoptic Circulation Patterns: Consequences for Extreme Event Attribution”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 47. DOI: [10.1029/2020GL088002](https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL088002).
- Fischer, Erich and Reto Knutti (Apr. 2015). “Anthropogenic contribution to global occurrence of heavy-precipitation and high-temperature extremes”. In: *Nature Climate Change* 5. DOI: [10.1038/NCLIMATE2617](https://doi.org/10.1038/NCLIMATE2617).
- Fowler, Hayley, Haider Ali, et al. (Mar. 2021). “Towards advancing scientific knowledge of climate change impacts on short-duration rainfall extremes”. In: *Philosophical transactions. Series A, Mathematical, physical, and engineering sciences* 379, p. 20190542. DOI: [10.1098/rsta.2019.0542](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2019.0542).
- Fowler, Hayley, Geert Lenderink, et al. (Jan. 2021). “Anthropogenic intensification of short-duration rainfall extremes”. In: *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*. DOI: [10.1038/s43017-020-00128-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-020-00128-6).
- Haruna, Abubakar et al. (June 2026). “Regional hotspots and contrasts in the trends of mean and extreme daily precipitation in France”. In: *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies* 65, p. 103378. DOI: [10.1016/j.ejrh.2026.103378](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrh.2026.103378).
- Hawkins, Harry and Stanley Rosenthal (Apr. 1965). “On the Computation of Stream Functions from the Wind Field”. In: *Monthly Weather Review - MON WEATHER REV* 93. DOI: [10.1175/1520-0493\(1965\)093<0245:OTCOSF>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1965)093<0245:OTCOSF>2.3.CO;2).
- Held, Isaac M. and Brian J. Soden (Nov. 2006). “Robust Responses of the Hydrological Cycle to Global Warming”. EN. In: *Journal of Climate* 19.21, pp. 5686–5699. ISSN: 0894-8755, 1520-0442. DOI: [10.1175/JCLI3990.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI3990.1). URL: <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/clim/19/21/jcli3990.1.xml> (visited on 04/21/2026).
- Hernandez, Valeria et al. (Aug. 2014). “Confronting Farmers’ Perceptions of Climatic Vulnerability with Observed Relationships between Yields and Climate Variability in Central Argentina”. In: *Weather, Climate, and Society* 7, pp. 39–59. DOI: [10.1175/WCAS-D-13-00062.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/WCAS-D-13-00062.1).
- Hettiarachchi, Suresh, Conrad Wasko, and Ashish Sharma (Mar. 2018). “Increase in flood risk resulting from climate change in a developed urban watershed – the role of storm temporal patterns”. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 22, pp. 2041–2056. DOI: [10.5194/hess-22-2041-2018](https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-22-2041-2018).

- Houze, Robert et al. (Aug. 2015). “The Variable Nature of Convection in the Tropics and Subtropics: A Legacy of 16 Years of the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) Satellite”. In: *Reviews of Geophysics*. DOI: [10.1002/2015RG000488](https://doi.org/10.1002/2015RG000488).
- Iliopoulou, Theano et al. (Jan. 2026). “Complexity of Hydroclimatic Changes in the Mediterranean: Exploring Climate Drivers Using ERA5 Reanalysis”. In: *Water* 18, p. 331. DOI: [10.3390/w18030331](https://doi.org/10.3390/w18030331).
- Janicot, Serge, Vincent Moron, and Bernard Fontaine (Mar. 1996). “Sahel droughts and ENSO dynamics”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters - GEOPHYS RES LETT* 23, pp. 515–518. DOI: [10.1029/96GL00246](https://doi.org/10.1029/96GL00246).
- Kiladis, George N. et al. (2009). “Convectively coupled equatorial waves”. en. In: *Reviews of Geophysics* 47.2. ISSN: 1944-9208. DOI: [10.1029/2008RG000266](https://doi.org/10.1029/2008RG000266). URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1029/2008RG000266> (visited on 06/04/2026).
- Knapp, Kenneth et al. (Mar. 2010). “The International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS): Unifying Tropical Cyclone Data”. In: *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 91, pp. 363–376. DOI: [10.1175/2009BAMS2755.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/2009BAMS2755.1).
- Koutsoyiannis, Demetris (Mar. 2010). “A random walk on water”. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 14, pp. 585–601. DOI: [10.5194/hess-14-585-2010](https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-14-585-2010).
- Latos, Beata et al. (Mar. 2026). “The Role of Equatorial Waves in Triggering Precipitation Extremes in the Maritime Continent”. In: *Monthly Weather Review* 154. DOI: [10.1175/MWR-D-25-0073.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-25-0073.1).
- Lenderink, Geert, Renaud Barbero, et al. (Aug. 2017). “Super-Clausius–Clapeyron Scaling of Extreme Hourly Convective Precipitation and Its Relation to Large-Scale Atmospheric Conditions”. In: *Journal of Climate* 30. DOI: [10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0808.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0808.1).
- Lenderink, Geert and Erik Meijgaard (July 2008). “Increase in hourly precipitation extremes beyond expectations from temperature”. In: *Nature Geoscience - NAT GEOSCI* 1, pp. 511–514. DOI: [10.1038/ngeo262](https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo262).
- Lesk, Corey and Justin Mankin (May 2026). “More concentrated precipitation decreases terrestrial water storage”. In: *Nature* 653, pp. 425–432. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-026-10487-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-026-10487-7).
- Li, Mei et al. (Feb. 2022). “Non-uniform changes in different daily precipitation events in the contiguous United States”. In: *Weather and Climate Extremes* 35, p. 100417. DOI: [10.1016/j.wace.2022.100417](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2022.100417).
- Li, Xiao and Han-Ru Cho (Sept. 1997). “Development and propagation of equatorial waves”. In: *Advances in Atmospheric Sciences - ADV ATMOS SCI* 14, pp. 323–338. DOI: [10.1007/s00376-997-0053-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00376-997-0053-6).
- Matsuno, Taroh (1966). “Quasi-Geostrophic Motions in the Equatorial Area”. In: *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II* 44.1, pp. 25–43. DOI: [10.2151/jmsj1965.44.1_25](https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj1965.44.1_25).
- Michelangeli, Paul-Antoine, Robert Vautard, and Bernard Legras (Apr. 1995). “Weather Regimes: Recurrence and Quasi Stationarity”. In: *J. Atmos. Sci.* 52, pp. 1237–1256. DOI: [10.1175/1520-0469\(1995\)052<1237:WRRASQ>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1995)052<1237:WRRASQ>2.0.CO;2).
- Miller, S. et al. (Sept. 2003). “Sea breeze: Structure, forecasting, and impacts”. In: *Reviews of Geophysics - REV GEOPHYS* 41. DOI: [10.1029/2003RG000124](https://doi.org/10.1029/2003RG000124).
- Molinié, Gilles et al. (Mar. 2012). “Rainfall Regime of a Mountainous Mediterranean Region: Statistical Analysis at Short Time Steps”. In: *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology* 51, pp. 429–448. DOI: [10.1175/2011JAMC2691.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/2011JAMC2691.1).
- Moncrieff, Mitchell and M.J. Miller (Apr. 1976). “The dynamics and simulation of tropical cumulonimbus and squall-lines”. In: 102, pp. 373–394.
- Morel, B. et al. (Aug. 2014). “Regionalizing Rainfall at Very High Resolution over La Reunion Island Using a Regional Climate Model”. In: *Monthly Weather Review* 142, pp. 2665–2686. DOI: [10.1175/MWR-D-14-00009.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-14-00009.1).
- Moron, Vincent, Renaud Barbero, Hayley Fowler, et al. (Mar. 2021). “Storm types in India: Linking rainfall duration, spatial extent and intensity”. In: *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A: Mathematical and physical sciences* 379. DOI: [10.1098/rsta.2020.0137](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0137).
- Moron, Vincent, Renaud Barbero, and Andrew Robertson (June 2015). “Subseasonal-to-interannual variability of rainfall over New Caledonia (SW Pacific)”. In: *Climate Dynamics*.
- Moron, Vincent, Erwan Cornillault, et al. (June 2025). “A climatology of local hourly wet spells across the tropics”. In: *Climate Dynamics* 63, p. 244. DOI: [10.1007/s00382-025-07714-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-025-07714-8).
- Moron, Vincent, Isabelle Gouirand, and Michael Taylor (July 2016). “Weather types across the Caribbean basin and their relationship with rainfall and sea surface temperature”. In: *Climate Dynamics* 47, pp. 601–621. DOI: [10.1007/s00382-015-2858-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-015-2858-9).
- Moron, Vincent and Andrew Robertson (May 2021). “Relationships between subseasonal-to-seasonal predictability and spatial scales in tropical rainfall”. In: *International Journal of Climatology* 41, pp. 5596–5624. DOI: [10.1002/joc.7143](https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.7143).
- Natoli, Michael and Eric Maloney (Sept. 2023). “Environmental Controls on the Tropical Island Diurnal Cycle in the Context of Intraseasonal Variability”. In: *Journal of Climate* 36, pp. 7465–7485. DOI: [10.1175/JCLI-D-22-0824.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-22-0824.1).
- Nesbitt, Stephen W. and Edward J. Zipser (May 2003). “The Diurnal Cycle of Rainfall and Convective Intensity according to Three Years of TRMM Measurements”. EN. In: *Journal of Climate* 16.10, pp. 1456–1475. ISSN: 0894-8755, 1520-0442. DOI: [10.1175/1520-0442\(2003\)016<1456:TDCORA>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2003)016<1456:TDCORA>2.0.CO;2); URL: https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/clim/16/10/1520-0442_2003_016_1456_tdcora_2.0.co_2.xml (visited on 06/10/2026).
- Obarein, Omon and Cameron Lee (Nov. 2025). “Extreme precipitation scaling under synoptic air mass regimes”. In: *Atmospheric Research* 331, p. 108647. DOI: [10.1016/j.atmosres.2025.108647](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2025.108647).
- Orlanski, Isidoro (1975). “A Rational Subdivision of Scales for Atmospheric Processes”. In: *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 56, pp. 527–530.
- Palmer, Tim and Renate Hagedorn (Jan. 2006). “Predictability of Weather Climate”. In: *Predictability of Weather and Climate, Edited by Tim Palmer and Renate Hagedorn. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006.* ISSN: 9780521848824. DOI: [10.1017/CB09780521848824](https://doi.org/10.1017/CB09780521848824).
- Pendergrass, Angeline and Dennis Hartmann (Nov. 2014). “Changes in the Distribution of Rain Frequency and Intensity in Response to Global Warming*.”. In: *Journal of Climate* 27, pp. 8372–8383. DOI: [10.1175/JCLI-D-14-00183.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-14-00183.1).
- Peyrille, Philippe, Romain Roehrig, and Sidiki Sanogo (Oct. 2023). “Tropical Waves Are Key Drivers of Extreme Precipitation Events in the Central Sahel”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 50. DOI: [10.1029/2023GL103715](https://doi.org/10.1029/2023GL103715).
- Prein, Andreas et al. (Apr. 2015). “A review on regional convection-permitting climate modeling: Demonstrations, prospects, and challenges: CONVECTION-PERMITTING CLIMATE MODELING”. In: *Reviews of Geophysics* 53, n/a–n/a. DOI: [10.1002/2014RG000475](https://doi.org/10.1002/2014RG000475).

- Ramirez Nina, Ronald, Maria Dias, and Pedro Silva Dias (May 2025). “Variability of the Diurnal Cycle of Precipitation in South America”. In: *Meteorology* 4, p. 13. DOI: [10.3390/meteorology4020013](https://doi.org/10.3390/meteorology4020013).
- Ribes, Aurélien et al. (Jan. 2019). “Observed increase in extreme daily rainfall in the French Mediterranean”. In: *Climate Dynamics* 52. DOI: [10.1007/s00382-018-4179-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-018-4179-2).
- Schlueter, Andreas et al. (Mar. 2019). “A Systematic Comparison of Tropical Waves over Northern Africa. Part I: Influence on Rainfall”. EN. In: *Journal of Climate* 32.5, pp. 1501–1523. ISSN: 0894-8755, 1520-0442. DOI: [10.1175/JCLI-D-18-0173.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-18-0173.1). URL: <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/clim/32/5/jcli-d-18-0173.1.xml> (visited on 06/04/2026).
- Shevchenko, Radomyra, Cathy Hohenegger, and Mira Schmitt (July 2023). “Impact of Diurnal Warm Layers on Atmospheric Convection”. In: *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 128. DOI: [10.1029/2022JD038473](https://doi.org/10.1029/2022JD038473).
- Straub, Katherine and George Kiladis (Feb. 2003). “Extratropical Forcing of Convectively Coupled Kelvin Waves during Austral Winter”. In: *Journal of The Atmospheric Sciences - J ATMOS SCI* 60, pp. 526–543. DOI: [10.1175/1520-0469\(2003\)060<0526:EF0CCK>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(2003)060<0526:EF0CCK>2.0.CO;2).
- Strommen, Kristian and Tim Palmer (Dec. 2018). “Signal and noise in regime systems: A hypothesis on the predictability of the North Atlantic Oscillation”. In: *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* 145. DOI: [10.1002/qj.3414](https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3414).
- Subrahmanyam, Kandula, Karanam kishore kumar, and Narendra Babu (Feb. 2015). “Phase relation between CAPE and precipitation at diurnal scales over the Indian summer monsoon region”. In: *Atmospheric Science Letters* 16. DOI: [10.1002/as12.566](https://doi.org/10.1002/as12.566).
- Tremblay, André (May 2005). “The Stratiform and Convective Components of Surface Precipitation”. In: *Journal of The Atmospheric Sciences - J ATMOS SCI* 62, pp. 1513–1528. DOI: [10.1175/JAS3411.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS3411.1).
- Trenberth, Kevin, Aiguo Dai, et al. (Sept. 2003). “The Changing Character of Precipitation”. In: *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 84, pp. 1205–1218. DOI: [10.1175/BAMS-84-9-1205](https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-84-9-1205).
- Trenberth, Kevin, Yongxin Zhang, and Maria Gehne (Mar. 2017). “Intermittency in Precipitation: Duration, Frequency, Intensity, and Amounts Using Hourly Data”. In: *Journal of Hydrometeorology* 18, pp. 1393–1412. DOI: [10.1175/JHM-D-16-0263.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JHM-D-16-0263.1).
- Verma, Utkarsh et al. (Apr. 2026). “Low level jet controlled dynamical and thermodynamical regimes of the diurnal cycle of rainfall over the western ghats”. In: *Environmental Research Communications* 8. DOI: [10.1088/2515-7620/ae5b4b](https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ae5b4b).
- Vicente-Serrano, Sergio et al. (Mar. 2025). “High temporal variability not trend dominates Mediterranean precipitation”. In: *Nature* 639, pp. 658–666. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-024-08576-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08576-6).
- Vitart, Frederic and Andrew Robertson (Mar. 2018). “The sub-seasonal to seasonal prediction project (S2S) and the prediction of extreme events”. In: *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* 1. DOI: [10.1038/s41612-018-0013-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-018-0013-0).
- Webster, Peter and James Holton (Apr. 1982). “Cross-Equatorial Response to Middle-Latitude Forcing in a Zonally Varying Basic State”. In: *Journal of The Atmospheric Sciences - J ATMOS SCI* 39, pp. 722–733. DOI: [10.1175/1520-0469\(1982\)039<0722:CERTML>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1982)039<0722:CERTML>2.0.CO;2).
- Wheeler, Matthew and George N. Kiladis (Feb. 1999). “Convectively Coupled Equatorial Waves: Analysis of Clouds and Temperature in the Wavenumber–Frequency Domain”. EN. In: *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences* 56.3, pp. 374–399. ISSN: 0022-4928, 1520-0469. DOI: [10.1175/1520-0469\(1999\)056<0374:CCEWAO>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1999)056<0374:CCEWAO>2.0.CO;2). URL: https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/atsc/56/3/1520-0469_1999_056_0374_ccewao_2.0.co_2.xml (visited on 06/04/2026).
- Wheeler, Matthew C. and Harry H. Hendon (Aug. 2004). “An All-Season Real-Time Multivariate MJO Index: Development of an Index for Monitoring and Prediction”. EN. In: *Monthly Weather Review* 132.8, pp. 1917–1932. ISSN: 1520-0493, 0027-0644. DOI: [10.1175/1520-0493\(2004\)132<1917:AARMMI>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(2004)132<1917:AARMMI>2.0.CO;2). URL: https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/mwre/132/8/1520-0493_2004_132_1917_aarmmi_2.0.co_2.xml (visited on 06/04/2026).
- Wong, Martin and Johnny Chan (Apr. 2006). “Tropical Cyclone Motion in Response to Land Surface Friction”. In: *Journal of The Atmospheric Sciences - J ATMOS SCI* 63, pp. 1324–1337. DOI: [10.1175/JAS3683.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS3683.1).
- Wu, Longtao et al. (June 2015). “Impact of environmental moisture on tropical cyclone intensification”. In: *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions* 15, pp. 16111–16139. DOI: [10.5194/acpd-15-16111-2015](https://doi.org/10.5194/acpd-15-16111-2015).
- Yang, Gui-Ying and Julia Slingo (Apr. 2001). “The Diurnal Cycle in the Tropics”. In: *Monthly Weather Review - MON WEATHER REV* 129. DOI: [10.1175/1520-0493\(2001\)129<0784:TDCITT>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(2001)129<0784:TDCITT>2.0.CO;2).

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List of Tables

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